

Master's Thesis

From the Digital Divide to Public Participation:
access, use, literacy, and perceived benefit in
social and political participation

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Global MPA Program on Local Government
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and Perceived Benefit in Social and Political Participation**

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ZARA**

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Abstract

From the Digital Divide to Public Participation: Access, Use, Literacy, and Perceived Benefit in Social and Political Participation

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Since the emergence of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), human societies have witnessed robust developments in this field. However, according to Digital Divide Index, half of the world's population is suffering from various types of digital divide. Afghanistan as a least developed country possesses the highest digital divide which might impede public participation in society, politics, and civic activities. Taking this fact into consideration, this study investigates the influence of the digital divide on the social and political participation of the citizens in Kabul Province, considering their socio-economic status. The required data of the study was collected through surveys of 354 citizens, utilizing stratified random sampling and purposive non-random sampling simultaneously, to reach out and include all sectors of the population, making the nature of this study, quantitative. This work is based on four leading theories in this field: Technological Determinism Theory, Diffusion of Innovation Theory,

Technology Acceptance Model, and Social Exclusion Theory. The collected data is analyzed using Ordinary Least Square Equation Modeling (OLS) and Bivariate Correlations. This study proved that there is a significant positive correlation between the digital divide, namely internet access, internet use, digital literacy, and perceived benefit dimensions and public participation domains. Accordingly, as an individual's level of digital divide decreases, the level of their public participation increases. Utilizing a comparative test of the physical and technical development and their effects on an individual's social and political participation, this study confirms the Technological Determinism Theory (TDT). The findings of this study may assist the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology, Ministry of Education, and other stakeholders to develop new ICT policies, minimize the digital gap, incorporate digital literacy in the education curriculum, and develop national connectivity.

Keywords: *Digital divide, internet access, internet use, digital literacy, perceived benefit, social participation, political participation, Technological Determinism Theory, Social Exclusion Theory, Technology Acceptance Model.*

I. INTRODUCTION

1. Background of the Study

The considerable contribution of ICT in the modern world is indisputable. The emergence of ICTs in the 1990s, extensive use of PCs, smartphones, and subsequent introduction of sophisticated technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, Blockchain, and Cloud revolutionized the way human societies look at everything, and the world has started to be the witness of robust positive changes in knowledge creation, quality of public services, education, health services, and so on. Among the mentioned areas, the adoption of e-Governance is of utmost importance, due to its leading role in the realization of the rest. Considering the importance of ICT, developing countries can effectively use this elixir to resolve their ongoing pressing problems.

It is now globally acknowledged that the world is increasingly moving into the information age, and the main component of this historic transition is information and communication technology (ICT) (Friedman, 2005). However, there is huge inequality in ICT access and use all over the world, which has been termed the “digital divide” (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2012; van Dijk, 2006).

Many LDCs applied the ICT-centric strategies and models of developed countries in their states to minimize the digital divide; however, because of the differences in the socio-economic, political, and technological environment, they failed, and their myriad problems remained unsolved. Analysts estimate that 35% of over 40 e-government projects in developing countries totally failed, 50% failed partially, and only 15% have succeeded (Meiyanti et al., 2019). These failures along with other socioeconomic factors

have widened the literacy and accessibility gaps between people and the technological revolution in their societies, which eventually hindered the equal and accessible delivery of services to citizens by the government.

Digital innovations and technological advancements have profoundly altered the ways people interact with their relatives, co-workers, community, and government, beginning from fundamental improvements in social media platforms, political campaigns to the evolution of electronic democracy. In addition, the development of emerging technologies has immensely contributed to knowledge creation, dissemination of information, and advancement of people's skills overall. As the internet and other means of communications have been extensively incorporated into each individual's daily life; this fact has increased public participation nationwide. In this study, I explore this premise by examining the impacts of the digital divide on various aspects of citizen engagement, including online civic participation, offline civic participation, offline political participation, and online political participation (Riel, 2012a).

Traditionally, the digital divide is characterized as the difference between those that use the Internet and those who do not, however recent conceptualizations of the digital divide include access, attitudes, skills, and usage types (J. E. Katz & Rice, 2002; van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014; Warschauer, 2003). The present study focuses on internet access, internet use, digital literacy, and perceived benefit aspects of the digital divide.

In Afghanistan, failure in the implementation of e-Government projects, extremely low internet penetration rate of approximately 20%, low digital literacy, and minimum adoption of recent technologies by people which have been identified as the key determinants of the digital divide inspired me to find out the roots and offer concerned

stakeholders a profound insight into the interrelationship factors affecting the digital divide in the mentioned context. Since the 'lack of physical infrastructure as the primary cause of digital divide' has been studied in earlier literature in Afghanistan, this work in addition to internet access, considers the internet use, digital literacy, and perceived benefit adapted from the Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) as the main subjects of its study under digital divide theme.

The "theory of uses and gratifications" suggests that media choice and exposure fulfill the social and psychological needs of people for gratification (Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch, 1973). This approach describes why people are committed and goal-oriented Internet users; they choose various Internet activities to satisfy their motives (Ruggiero, 2000). For example, people use the Internet for fun and amusement to satisfy their leisure motivation, to find information to learn new things on the Internet to fulfill their personal development motives, and to interact with friends on social media in order to satisfy their belonging needs (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014). Therefore, the uses and gratifications theory support the classification of Internet usage types developed from the most common contemporary Internet activities.

The literature has discussed the evolvments of emerging digital skills and has answered the questions of how the rise of information and communication technologies has expanded traditional notions of literacy? and how this transition has affected society?

Literacy and communication abilities have been related to greater levels of public participation (Wilhelm, 2000). It can be basically defined as the familiarity or ability to efficiently use electronic tools internet-based devices to find information, create content, disseminate, and share the information with others.

Literacy skills, which are part of a greater set of “civic skills,” (or the ability to communicate efficiently in public contexts) have been identified to be strong antecedent skills for participation (Brady, Verba, & Schlozman, 1995). Nevertheless, this environment has also shown an increase in the complexity of information analysis and technical skills needed to receive balanced and exact information with which to make decisions (Sunstein, 2007; Jamieson & Cappella, 2008; Stroud, 2011). New skills that expand the concept of traditional literacy are needed in order to interpret the large amounts of digital information within different multimedia applications.

Scholars argue that familiarity with digital technologies is important for a powerful civic life (Gee, 2008; Martin, 2010). Digital literacy scholars propose that a digitally literate person should not only be aware of how to operate the technology yet should also understand the social setting under which information is created and the boundaries of the media in which information is presented (Gee, 2008; Lankshear & Knobel, 2006; Kress, 2003). In the light of this, measures of digital literacy should not only contain mastery of discrete technological abilities, but also a broader knowledge of the origins and bias of information (Riel, 2012a).

Public participation which is referred to as the engagement in any online and offline social, civic, and political activities; typically entails activities to socialize, to influence the people, or to affect social or political reforms, such as attending community events, joining social groups, discussing political issues, or signing petitions to the government to affect a policy decision. Scholars have studied various domains of public participation. In this thesis, I have focused on its two main domains, social participation, and political participation.

During the first years of the internet, people without access to digital technologies were related to lower levels of participation (Norris, 2001; Warschauer, 2003; Van Dijk, 2005). As broadcast media became important in America, scholars have increasingly associated mass media use with low levels of mass participation and higher levels of social isolation (Putnam, 2000). However, with the rise of the Internet as a new platform for social interaction, scholars have discovered that the Internet does not necessarily isolate users, but rather fosters the advancement of digitally mediated communities with modern types of participation as a result (Putnam & Feldstein, 2003; Zukin, et al., 2006). Principally because of the increased ability to collect information and connect with other people, scholars propose that a new form of citizenship has emerged (Zukin, et al., 2006). An example of an antecedent condition for engagement is political and social knowledge, as those with greater levels of knowledge of political and social affairs demonstrate higher levels of participation (Galston, 2001; Milner, 2002; Prior, 2007). Additionally, civic education programs that aim to enhance knowledge also result in higher levels of mass participation (Finkel, 2003).

Political participation is the right to speak out, communicate, the ability to engage in the conduct of public affairs, and the ability to register as a candidate, to be elected, to vote, and to hold office at all levels of government arise from political involvement. Political engagement goes beyond parties, however. Through independent action, especially at the local level, and by joining civil society groups, individuals can also get involved in some aspects of the democratic process. For political engagement, professional networks, labor unions, non-governmental organizations, and the media may all provide avenues (UN, 2005).

2. Problem Statement

In spite of the fact that recently the world has been witnessed robust development in this field; however, according to Digital Divide Index, half of the world's population are suffering from different types of the digital divide: among all these countries Afghanistan, as a least developed country, possess highest digital divide.

In Afghanistan, the slow pace of ICT development has become a case for analysis in public policy and academic discourse. Many factors have been pointed out in previous studies as challenges to ICT development. Of the many bottlenecks that impede the success of this sector, security and corruption are the most prominent ones in the country. Other main problems that are related to this study are the lack of innovative leadership, high cost of telecommunications services, lack of expertise, issues with rough terrain and geographical location of the country, and more importantly lack of motivation of the people in using ICT means extensively.

In Afghanistan, the Ministry of Communications, and Information Technology (MCIT), Afghanistan Telecom Regulatory Authority (ATRA), and National Statistics and Information Authority (NISA) are the main bodies of the government that have direct responsibility for ICT innovation and digitalization of the country. Among those, the Ministry of ICT, despite civic conflicts and political instability, has developed and implemented various crucial e-government initiatives in order to narrow the “digital divide” and provide citizens with trustworthy, effective, and accountable public services (Afghanistan National Development Strategy 2008). In recent years, a handful of projects have been developed in multiple regions of the country; however, the implemented

projects usually solve the digital divide issues temporarily. Sustainability of the ICT-oriented projects is one of the key challenges in the country, that on one hand wastes the invested capital and on the other hand, does not affect the digital divide.

Afghanistan is a unitary democratic country where most of the local public officials are being selected through people's votes. However, when it comes to policy making, the participation of the public is at its minimum level. In this study, I will explore the level of the digital divide in Kabul province and the degree to which it affects public participation in society.

3. Purpose of the Study

The study is seeking to assess the relationships between the digital divide (independent variables) and public participation (dependent variable) controlling socio-economic status at Kabul Province, as the research site. The independent variables are the four dimensions of the digital divide that are: internet access, internet use, digital literacy, and technology perceived benefit. The dependent variable is the two domains of public participation that are: social participation and political participation. As for the controlling variables, age, gender, education level, income level was being studied.

Failure in the implantation of e-Government projects as the supply side and minimum technology adoption attitude among the people (the so-called demand side) in the least developed countries, especially in Afghanistan, where I came from, motivated me to find out the roots concerning digital divide and e-governance in the first step and examine its consequences on public participation subsequently.

One of the major goals of this work is to develop an overarching theoretical model

of the digital divide and public participation for Kabul city which will be containing major domains of each in order to support the government of Afghanistan and other concerned stakeholders in institutionalizing the ICT-centric initiatives in the country. With this aim in mind, this paper attempts to examine the national status quo of internet access, internet use, digital literacy, and technology perceived benefit, to explore the digital divide factors affecting or hindering citizens' participation, and to analyze the consequences of the presence of the digital divide on ICT adoption of the citizens while considering the social-economic variables.

Overall, the main purpose of this study is to investigate the perceptions of the demand side to answer the following research question: *To what degree does the digital divide influences various dimensions of public participation?*

Based on the results of the analysis, this study would then provide the stakeholders with policy proposals for planning, decision-making, and policy recommendations for the sustainable development of ICTs in Afghanistan and developing countries.

4. Significance of the Study

This research primarily contributes to the implementation and adoption of various e-Government policies and systems in the country by the government sector. Since the study focuses on the digital divide, the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology (MCIT), Afghanistan Telecom Regulatory Authority (ATRA), and National Statistic and Information Authority (NSIA), as the main ICT policy-makers and other concerned civil servants will benefit because they can make use of the research in developing new e-Government policies or projects in the researched site.

This research has a number of novel attributes in comparison to existing literature. While much of the previous literature on the digital divide has concentrated on access, use, and digital literacy aspects, acknowledging them as prerequisites to public participation, few studies have thoroughly examined the relationships of perceived benefit that includes cultural and motivational aspects of the digital divide that might be needed for increased mass participation in the Internet Age. More importantly, no research has been conducted pertinent to the subject matter in the Afghanistan context so far.

5. Theoretical Perspective

This study is mainly based on four important theories, namely the Technology Acceptance Model, Technology Determinism Theory, Diffusion of Innovation Theory, and Social Exclusion Theory.

Smith and Marx (1996) argued that the digital divide debate is originally considered as an aspect of Technological Determinism Theory (TDT). It is a technology-based theory of social change; in which, technology – technical development – is perceived as the main driver and principal determinant of human relations, culture, and social structure, whereas the social factors are considered secondary.

Taking the fact that not all changes are as a result of technology, the need for another approach to explain the motives why some groups of people tend to adopt novel technologies, and some do not, was sensed. Everett Rogers (2003) supporting the Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT), argues that the emergence of technology itself is not the only reason which motivates the people to adopt it ‘en mass’. The mentioned theory seeks to find out why, where, and to what quality the emerging technologies spread.

He, contrary to technological determinists, goes beyond and proposes three other elements that foster the spread of technology: the innovative technology itself, communication channel, first adopters, first majority, and late majority. Rogers' arguments are very close to that of Tichenor who developed the knowledge gap hypothesis (Donohue and Olien, 1970; Everett Rogers, 2003). The majority of scholars, supporting this hypothesis, propose that during the study of the digital divide, both 'access' and 'use' should be considered equally (Srinuan, 2012).

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) which was introduced in 1986, explains the main factors that provoke users to accept technology the acceptance of information technology by its users (Davis, 1989). According to the model, two beliefs affect the user's decision for accepting the newly introduced technology, namely: "Perceived Usefulness & Perceived Ease of Use.

6. Research Method

To obtain accurate results of the public's perception, the participants must be selected randomly. In citizen-based survey research, the word "random" is very important. If a sample is selected randomly, all individuals in the population have equal opportunities of being chosen. The reason that randomness is so crucial is that a random selection is possibly to be fairly representative of the population from which it was selected. When a sample of people is chosen randomly and then asked questions, we can be fairly sure that the opinions expressed will be close to the entire population.

One of the key challenges of this research has to do with lack of the list of the entire population in order to perform a probabilistic random sampling. The full list of the

population of Kabul Province is not available in any source. When there is no list, according to scholars, the researchers can still keep the randomness of the sample.

In this research, since the list of the entire population was not accessible to draw sample; therefore, the city is divided into various areas called Primary Sampling Units (PSUs). Each selected PSU is then divided into smaller regions. On a regular basis, the researcher has to sub-divide those smaller regions into city blocks or rural areas and then select people from those final blocks or areas randomly. However, the author chose to conduct a purposive sampling technique that is less time-consuming and more cost-efficient. This technique has also been used in recent researches on internet use and digital surveys as well (Reddick et al., 2020; Akombwa & Tembo, 2020; Haines, 2020; Miranda et al., 2013).

The required data were collected utilizing survey questionnaires through an *intercept survey* approach that is used to collect on-site feedback from respondents at academic institutions, literacy centers, events, religious activities (Mosques), shopping malls, and so on in every district of the Kabul Province separately to have an inclusive sample.

7. Scope and Limitations of the Study

The digital divide is a complex multidimensional concept which is a result of various social, economic, political, environmental, and even natural factors that should be indebtedly examined. Previous literature has indebtedly gone through factors causing the digital divide, such as infrastructure, literacy, and use, however, has paid minimum attention to the perceived benefit, motivational and cultural aspects of it.

In addition, the existing studies have indebtedly considered factors causing a digital

divide, such as local economy, infrastructure, and demography, but have paid no attention to the political context and security challenges in crisis-hit countries. In war-torn countries, where local people typically suffer from insecurity, the issue of digitization does not seem to be considered as their key priority, even though the economy affords it, and the infrastructure is available. The second reason is associated with rough nature. Some rural areas are located far enough away from the local government and separated by rugged mountains from technology centers that hinder successful ICT penetration. A third criticism of previous studies could represent the lack of attention to a series of intergovernmental and out-of-state circles who consider the implementation of large-scale technological projects as a risk to their interests and strive to prevent the implementation of such projects, which consequences nothing but a heightened digital divide. The above limitations could equally fit into the questions that future researchers can respond to.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Public participation in society is commonly regarded as the main sign of a healthy democracy, and Afghanistan as a newborn democracy requires the participation of the public as a source of transformational ideas. Public participation has developed from the traditional notion of participation with the development of information technologies. Nowadays, access and familiarity with technological means could be an indicator of social influence if it is incorporated in the participation process.

The expansion of information and communication technologies into the realm of mass participation has increasingly encouraged researchers over the last twenty years. Much of these studies explore the types of activities in which the public participates, the types of media utilized, and the various socio-economic factors that encourage participation. The literature also delves into the various types of knowledge and prerequisite skills that are needed for influential and informed public participation in communities.

I, in this chapter, highlight past literature on the digital divide, public participation, description of digital adoption theories, and their relationships with public participation. First of all, I examine the concept of the digital divide, its determinants and will define the four important domains of the digital divide this thesis is going to analyze. Second, I review the four domains of mass participation and how they have been reflected in the existing literature. Next, I will elaborate on the current context of Afghanistan and the influencing socio-demographic factors that might affect variables of this thesis. Finally, I will state the research questions that are used as a guide for this study.

1. Digital divide

Since the emergence of information and communication technologies, the digital divide has enjoyed a rich history of discussion and research. According to Van Dijk (2000), the concept of the digital divide is a complex and dynamic phenomenon that was introduced and became popular in the 1990s. OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) defines digital divide as “the gap between individuals, households, businesses and geographic areas at different socioeconomic levels with regard both to their opportunities to access ICTs and to their use of the Internet for a wide variety of activities” (OECD, 2001).

The digital divide typically means access gaps depending on socio-economic divides (Alexander J.A.M. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2015). In recent years, the digital divide discourse has centered on acquiring the skills required for safe and productive usage of the Internet, also called the second-level digital divide (Hargittai, 2002). In addition, some scholars have divided the digital divide into the first and second-level digital divide concerning the huge inequality in ICT access and use (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2012; van Dijk, 2006; Dewan & Riggins, 2005; Keil, 2018; Büchi et al., 2016; Hargittai & Hsieh, 2013).

According to Loader et al., the key determinant of the digital divide is the extent of physical access to ICTs and the internet that can be achieved through ICT infrastructure development (Loader et al., 2004). LDCs can adopt essential affordable means firstly, like mobile internet, telecenters, community service centers, and radio, information kiosks, etc. (Okunola et al., 2017; Upadhyaya, 2019). Analysis on the basis of the location showed rural citizens have limited access to e-Government services and ICT means, whereas the level of access in urban areas was high. The same fact applies to the citizens’

experience as well (Srinuan, 2012).

Professor Jan Van Dijk of Twente University elaborates on the process of how a person starts using technology. He states that access to digital means such as computers and the internet starts with a motivation and a positive attitude towards using those technologies. Subsequently, people need physical access through getting a type of computer and or Internet connection. It is not enough: the next step is to grow a series of digital skills. Subsequent to this phase people can use all types of applications that are relevant to them. Lastly, they look to find the benefits of using these media, and of course, the impacts and outcomes of using technological means are the main goals of this process (Alexander & van Dijk, 2017).

The key effect of the digital divide is that citizens have unequal access to knowledge, information, and other opportunities that can lead to more general socioeconomic inequality and disparities in power (Bonfadelli, 2002). On the supply side, the lack of government technical capability and weak collaboration between university research and R&D in e-government initiatives are among the factors mentioned barriers to ICT growth (Upadhyaya, 2019). Failure in collaboration with the above-mentioned institutions leads to the unavailability of local content and raises fears about ‘western’ content in some cultural-oriented countries (Genus & Nor, 2007).

Concerning gender and age, findings suggest that women and elderly people are decreasingly likely to use ICT facilities than men and youth (Wasserman & Richmond-Abbott, 2005; Antonio & Tuffley, 2014; Okunola et al., 2017; Srinuan, 2012). The socio-demographic variables on the usage of ICT are also considered. For instance, interviewees with better education, job, and higher income have reported greater access to digital

facilities, which in turn leads to an increased level of previous internet experience (Okunola et al., 2017; Srinuan, 2012). The best way would be to train young members of the community about the benefits of ICTs who, in turn, can raise awareness for others (Srinuan, 2012, Babu et al., 2012, Upadhyaya, 2019).

1.1. Levels of Digital Divide

In order to use modern technology, one should first be motivated to use it. When adequate motivation is created, one should be able to obtain physical access to a digital device (such as a computer or smartphone), the Internet, or another digital medium. In addition, material resources are required to continue utilizing technology consisting of peripheral equipment, software, ink, paper, subscriptions, etc. Having physical and material access does not necessarily lead to the appropriation of technology, as one should first develop necessary skills for the use of the medium. The further these skills are developed; the more appropriate use will be made of the technology (J. A. G. M. Van Dijk, 2012).

For the last 25 years, digital divide research and policy have focused on three levels. Until the year 2010, physical access to computers and the internet was the main area of interest for both researchers and policymakers. The main objective was to have some type of computer and Internet connection for everybody. This level is called the First Level of the digital divide in literature. In the course of time, both researchers and policymakers agreed that digital literacy, skills, and usage are in fact more significant in talks about digital inequality. This is called the Second Level digital divide. Since 2015, the outcomes of internet and computer use have moved to the Third Level of digital divide research and

policy. It was the time that not only positive outcomes were noticed but also negative ones such as the internet or game addiction, illegal hacking, cybercrime, and dissemination of hate speech and disinformation on the social media (Alexander & van Dijk, 2017).

The four phases of access are the principle of a theory about the digital divide called *Resources and Appropriation theory* evaluated in many surveys throughout the last 25 years by many authors. The main argument of this theory is that personal and positional categories of individuals have more or less particular resources in pursuing this four phases process and its outcomes or impacts, a process called *appropriation of technology*. This model and all its factors are fitting to the data in many countries. This process is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: “Four Successive Kinds of Access in the Appropriation of Digital

Technology” (J. A. G. M. Van Dijk, 2012; Alexander & van Dijk, 2017)

1.2. Internet Access

The vast majority of digital divide research are devoted to the study of physical access divided to personal computers and the Internet between demographic categories that are: income, education, age, gender, and ethnicity. Van Dijk studied differential access and characteristics of individuals to information and computing technology (ICTs) and related them to *personal categorical inequality* factors as below: “age (young/old); gender (male/female); race/ethnicity (majority/minority); Intelligence (high/low); personality (extravert/introvert; self-confident/not self-confident); health (abled/disabled). The same applies to the following positional categorical inequalities: Labor position (entrepreneurs/workers; management/employees; employed /unemployed); education (high/low); household (family/single person); nation (developed/developing)” (J. A. G. M. Van Dijk, 2012).

Van Dijk and Vann Deursen go beyond the traditional definition of access and define it as access is a multidimensional concept that ranges from physical access to content, skills, motivation, the flexibility of usage, the quantity of use, and forms of internet use (Alexander J.A.M. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2015).

Norris states that the gap in access to ICT could be seen with three distinct dimensions, which includes a global divide (refers to ICT gap between nations), a social divide (refers to the disparity in ICT access among various groups in society), and a democratic divide (refers to the disparity in the use of a variety of digital means to benefit the civil rights) (Norris, 2001).

The gap in the developed countries of America and Eastern Asia began to decline as high-income groups and education entered partial saturation, and people with lower incomes and education began to catch up; nevertheless, in developing countries, the physical access gap has continued to widen and is still expanding.

Van Dijk (2012), in his book *The Deepening Divide*, has developed a theory-based rational view of social inequality, which named it “a resources and appropriation theory diffusion, acceptance and adoption of new technologies”. He explains the four concepts of this theory as below:

1. Many personal and positional categorical inequalities in society
2. The distribution of resources relevant to this type of inequality
3. Many kinds of access to ICTs
4. Many fields of participation in society

“1 and 2 are held to be the causes, and 3 is the phenomenon to be explained, together with 4, the potential consequence of the whole process. Being part of a process, 4 feeds back upon 1 and 2, as more or less participation in several fields of society will change the relationships of categorical inequalities and the distribution of resources in society. Finally, the fifth state of affairs determining the type of inequality to be explained has to be added as a side factor: the special characteristics of information and communication technology. In this way, a dynamic model can be drawn that forms the representation of this theory.” (J. A. G. M. Van Dijk, 2012).

Figure 2: “Causal Model of Resources and Appropriation Theory”

(Alexander J.A.M. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2015)

The core argument of this model can be summarized in the following statements:

- 1) In society, categorical inequalities generate an unequal distribution of resources.
- 2) Unequal resource distribution led to unequal access to digital means.
- 3) Unequal access to new technology is also based on the features and characteristics of those technologies;
- 4) unequal access to digital technologies causes unequal engagement in society;
- 5) Unequal social engagement promotes categorical inequality and unequal wealth distribution.

1.3. Internet Use

Having sufficient motivation, physical access, and skills to apply digital media are necessary but not sufficient conditions of actual use, because digital use has its own factors and determinants (J. A. G. M. Van Dijk, 2012).

Numerous studies illustrate how internet use depends on different biological,

economic, social, or organizational factors in the general population. Age is adversely linked to internet usage, but higher education, higher income, having a career, marital status is correlated with higher internet use. (Scholz et al., 2017). As for the gender gap, which is getting closer in most of the developed countries but still, women use the internet lesser than men for different reasons (Robinson et al., 2015; Hargittai, 2006).

The "theory of uses and gratifications" suggests that media choice and exposure fulfill the social and psychological needs of people for gratification (E. Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch, 1973, 1974). This approach describes why people are committed and goal-oriented Internet users; they choose various Internet activities to satisfy their motives (Ruggiero, 2000). For example, people use the Internet for fun and amusement to satisfy their leisure motivation, to find information to learn new things on the Internet to fulfill their personal development motives and to interact with friends on social media in order to satisfy their belong needs (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014). Therefore, the uses and gratifications theory support the classification of Internet usage types developed from the most common contemporary Internet activities. Two theoretical proposals derive from the above paragraph: (a) Internet usage by an individual is represented by a set of Internet activities that includes leisure, shopping, government services, social networking, study, career, news, and gaming; and (b) offline activities differ across a set of Internet uses (Ng et al., 2019).

Earlier research has clustered Internet users into categories by their Internet activities, such as interacting with friends, playing games, and ordering goods online (e.g., Brandtzæg, Heim, & Karahasanović, 2011; Brandtzæg, 2010). For example, Egea et al. (2007) Conducted a cluster study and confirmed five categories of internet users in

Europe: 44% non-Internet users who rarely use the Internet; 19% who regularly use public services but do not shop mostly on the Internet; 19% advanced internet users who frequently use the Internet for different online activities; 16% laggards who sometimes use online government services and seldom use the internet for personal purpose, and 2% others who have difficulties in using the internet. Later, Brandtzæg et al. (2011) Identified five related categories of Internet users: 42% who use the Internet on a non-regular basis; 18% users who are occasional Internet users; 18% strategic users who use the Internet for goal-oriented reasons; 12% specialized users who are frequent Internet users; and 10% media users who use the Internet to watch drama. The classification of various Internet usage groups allows detailed characterization of variations in complex online behavior (Johnson & Kulpa, 2007).

Van Dijk (2012) states that digital use as a dependent factor can be measured in four ways: “usage time and frequency; number and diversity of usage applications; broadband or narrowband use; more or less active or creative use.”

In this thesis, I have chosen the first two ways as an indicator to measure internet use. In the United States and European countries, exact measures of daily, weekly, or monthly digital use are used in some annual surveys. According to Van Dijk, the most reliable and valid measurement of actual usage time can be made on a “daily” basis.

An important usage factor is usage time, which was studied in 2010 by van Deursen and van Dijk on Dutch people. For the first time in history, the study showed that people with low education levels were using the Internet in their free time more hours a day than those with high education levels, precisely 3.2 hours a day compared to 2.6 hours. Compared to the situation in the 1980s and 1990s when the use was completely dominated

by the highly educated, this turned the use time of computer and the internet by different social classes pertinent to education completely upside down.

These results support the study proposed by van Dijk on the existence of a so-called use gap in terms of computer and Internet use (J. van Dijk, 1999; J. Van Dijk, 2002). The basic statement is that some parts of the population will use more frequently important applications with the highest beneficial effects on income and resources (work, career, study, socialization, involvement, etc.), whereas other sections will use amusement applications with no or very little, beneficial effects on capital and resources. This argument was then extended to low- and high-education individuals, thereby framing the educational use gap.

The thesis is directly connected to the knowledge gap thesis of the 1970s that highly educated people gained more knowledge from mass media such as television and newspapers than low-educated ones. In terms of social inequality, only the use gap is much greater and theoretically more powerful than the knowledge gap because the usage gap includes unequal uses and activities in all areas of everyday life, not just mass media awareness (Van Dijk, 2012).

1.4. Digital Literacy

Since public participation has assumed a new form as a result of the utilization of information technology, the skills and expertise needed for mass participation have also changed. Digital literacy, the ability to effectively use digitally networked tools to find, evaluate, create, share, and synthesize electronic information, is regularly regarded by

education/literary scholars as a rising skill set for the general public. The literature on digital literacy largely theorizes the various kinds of skills required for a digitally literate person.

Before digital literacy arose as a research subject of its own, researchers on "new literacy" theorized that plural literacy skills exist. Understanding of plural pieces of literature began to replace the more traditional definition of literacy which is "the basic ability to read and write" (Kress, 2003; Cope and Kalantzis, 2000; Snyder, 2002).

Plural literacies not only reflect the ability to translate and create language in various ways, but also the mastery of the instruments through which people interact and the social context under which communication is being used. As such, literature scholars also say that there is no standard overarching definition of literacy skills across domains, as these skills are social and contextual (Gee, 2008). Plural literacies are characterized not only by the possession of distinct abilities but also by the mastery of communications activities or processes in a situational context (Lankshear & Knobel, 2006). Both tangible and measurable skills (the skill to read and write) and other intangible capabilities are included in this notion of literacy (the ability to interpret communications according to social context or to think critically). Since language itself is just as crucial as the media by which the language is coded and decoded, both the communication platform and the information contained in the tools are considered important.

As public participation has taken a new form resulting from the information and communication technologies, likely, the relevant skills and expertise needed for mass participation have also changed. Recent Internet Adoption theorization acknowledges that a binary physical connectivity classification does not reflect the scope of what it means

to be online. An increasing number of scholars argue that the skills aspects of Internet interaction and how these aspects apply to various forms of social exclusion should also be taken into account (A. J. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014; A. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2011; Warschauer, 2003) As a result, digital inclusion policies have been developed in many countries to promote internet skills of individuals (Alexander J.A.M. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2015).

In a public participation sense, Brady, Verba, and Schlozman measured literacy and communication skills by developing an index to assess civic skills as it is related to political participation. Skills such as the capacity to read, write and communicate as well as the ability to coordinate, engage in meetings, and work in groups were included in this index. They argued that these abilities have a positive effect on the capacity of an individual for public participation. As new media and other emerging technologies increasingly became accessible, nevertheless, the definitions of communication skills and what it meant by being literate were changed in the 21st century which gave rise to digital literacy. The style, techniques, resources, and language used when interacting in digital environments are best described by digital literacy, something that the concept of traditional literacy is not flexible enough to reflect (Brady et al., 1995).

Van Deursen and van Dijk presented six types of internet skills and several types of measurements: operational, formal, information and strategic (A. J.A.M. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2010; Alexander J.A.M. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2015; Van Dijk, 2012).

Figure 3: “Six types of digital skills applied to Internet skills”

(J. A. G. M. Van Dijk, 2012)

Considering the above model, the only way to achieve a true and full assessment of digital skills is to evaluate computer and internet-related activities that are routinely done in everyday life by individuals. In this thesis, five domains of this model are analyzed as below: operational skills, information skills, communication skills, content creation skills, and strategic skills.

Fundamental computer skills provide the technical foundation for the effective use of any information technologies, which are in general vital for any higher-order digital literacy mastery (International Technology Education Association, 2002; Jenkins, 2006a; Trilling & Fadel, 2009). Dudeney et al. (2014) define mobile literacy as “the ability to navigate, interpret information from, contribute information to, and communicate through the mobile internet, including an ability to orient oneself in the space of the internet of things (where information from real-world objects is integrated into the net) and

augmented reality (where web-based information is overlaid on the real world)”. Basic information processing skills deal with the theoretical assumption that users of information and communications technologies should also be capable of critically obtaining, analyzing, and using information effectively. Scholars state that without information skills, users of information technologies will be incompetent to make sense of the deluge of information that is available to users (Gilster, 1997; Rushkoff, 2010; Bawden, 2001; Snavely & Cooper, 1997). The domains of communication skills (the skill to send and receive information) and publication skills (the skill to create new information) deal with the delivery and sharing functions that information technologies offer. Scholars hold that the ability to appropriately interpret messages within various media, elect the proper medium for communication or expression, and merge media for various effects are essential for a digitally literate person (Jenkins, 2006b; Buckingham, 2003). Safety and adequate knowledge to protect the data from being stolen or having the literacy to distinguish between a web link and a fake link are also added to the study to find out how vulnerable people are.

The above-mentioned five domains of digital literacy that I have selected for this thesis all benefit a person’s capability for self-expression and conveyance of his/her ideas or social needs. In this thesis, I argue that digital literacy is essential for people to engage in their society in order to bring about social and political reforms through social and political activities. By analyzing data from a quantitative survey for this study, I elaborate that digital literacy can serve as a strong indicator of public participation and will prove that it has become an important skill that empowers citizens to play their role in the modern participation environment.

As mentioned in the above sections, researchers have shown a growing need for the public to develop a mastery of skills in technology and information processing. Thus, several computing, information, and other technology skills falling under the digital literacy category have become a precondition skill set for mass participation. This is particularly true as public institutions boost their use of information technology, as schools introduce the teaching of these skills into the curriculum, as election campaigns are increasingly digitally mediated, and as democratic dialogue needs online platforms and not just face-to-face interactions.

1.5. Perceived Benefit

The desire to have a device and to be linked to the Internet comes prior to physical access. Many of those who stay on the 'wrong' side of the digital divide have motivation issues. It seems that considering digital technologies, “there are not only 'have-nots' but also 'want-nots’”. Access to digital means such as computers and the internet starts with a motivation and a positive attitude for using these means. Of course, the outcomes of using digital media are the main objective of the process. As per Van Dijk, people use technology and digital means in the hope to find the benefits of these technologies. (Alexander & van Dijk, 2017).

Since the introduction of modern technologies, motivational challenges are still the biggest. In the 1980s and 1990s, several individuals replied to survey questions that they are not in need of a computer or internet connection. The desire to acquire a computer and access the Internet rapidly rises as technology diffuses widely throughout society.

American surveys revealed that the key reasons for the refusal of having technology were: “no need or significant usage opportunities”; “no time or liking”; “rejection of the medium” (the Internet and computer games as ‘dangerous’ media); lack of money; and lack of skills (J. A. G. M. Van Dijk, 2012).

The factors that explain motivational access are social or cultural as well as mental or psychological in essence. As Katz and Rice argue that "the Internet has no attraction for low-income and low-educated individuals" (Katz and Rice, 2002).

2. Public Participation

The terms “participation” or “engagement” and “Public” or “Mass” have a minor difference in meaning, however, in this thesis, they are used interchangeably. Engagement refers to actively engaging and exchanging ideas and opinions, while participation may only be a meeting without an exchange.

Similar to the digital divide, public participation has also been studied thoroughly by researchers and social science scholars. Simply, public participation is the engagement of the public in civic, political, and social activities. In a general term, public participation is comprised of the activities carried out for socialization, influencing people, or bringing about social and political changes, such as, effecting social reforms through demonstrations or using petition right to change certain policy decisions.

“Public participation is not a one-time event; it is a continues series of initiatives conducted by people and promoted in a persistent and sustainable manner by governing bodies. The desired result of civic participation often contributes to citizens' happiness as their needs are met. Five stages of the public participation process have been established

by the International Association for Public Participation (IAPP), which facilitates public participation in government decision-making around the globe: inform, consult, engage, collaborate and empower. (Najimi, 2018).

Figure 4:
International Association for Public Participation (Source: www.iap2.org)

As research on public participation expanded, scholars have described other preconditions and antecedent skills in greater detail that affect the capacity and interest of an individual in mass participation. These preconditions and skills include access to information technology, influence, political and civic knowledge, information exposure, literacy, and communication skills. (Riel, 2012a).

For several years, *access to resources* has been a strong indicator of participation. Those with higher levels of time, money, or social influence are typically more involved than those without such resources. (Verba, Schlozman, Brady, 1995; Lijphart, 1997). In addition, those without access to technical instruments for communication or media consumption are less likely to participate as information technology has become increasingly incorporated into mass participation activities. (Norris, 2001; Warschauer,

2003; van Dijk, 2005).

During the first years of the internet, people without access to digital technologies were related to lower levels of participation (Norris, 2001; Warschauer, 2003; Van Dijk, 2005). As broadcast media became important in America, scholars have increasingly associated mass media use with low levels of public participation and higher levels of social isolation (Putnam, 2000). However, with the rise of the Internet as a new platform for social interaction, scholars have discovered that the Internet does not necessarily isolate users, but rather fosters the advancement of digitally mediated communities with modern types of participation as a result (Putnam & Feldstein, 2003; Zukin, et al., 2006).

Similar to the political knowledge gathering activities, the public's exposure to information is another predictor for higher public participation. Zukin, et al (2006), in what they call cognitive involvement and outline this form of context precondition for public participation. Cognitive participation is the way in which people pay attention to civic and political knowledge or are subjected to it but do not generally take overt action on policy and public relations issues.

In this section, social participation and political participation, as two domains of public participation, being examined in this thesis, will be further elaborated.

The social participation domain of participation is an important aspect regarding the research of public participation, though some scholars contend that political participation might be more important for democratic health (Zukin, et al., 2006).

Social participation is defined as in-person and voluntary activities in which an individual has a hand in or shares activities for personal growth and common benefits but does not necessarily pursue the social change or problem-solving outcomes that are being

demonstrated by activities in the civic participation realm. Some activities under the social membership participation domain include joining clubs, organizations, hobby groups, or other membership-oriented groups (Riel, 2012a).

Online social participation has become an emerging avenue for social activities as the Internet progressively serves as a medium for interpersonal communication tool. Digital communication means and devices provide the opportunity for real-time sharing, cross-geographical connections, and profound exchange that can encourage social life and public discourse. Nowadays, even some social activities may take place exclusively on digital platforms. Similar to the offline social participation domain mentioned above, online social participation can be defined as a set of voluntary activities in which an individual participates or shares in activities for personal growth, common interests, or leisure but does so only via networked electronic devices. Activities in this domain include participation in online education, forums, online dating, online games, and other activities for sharing information that is mediated especially via the Internet (Jenkins, 2006b; Coleman & Blumler, 2009).

Political participation is the right to speak out, communicate, the ability to engage in the conduct of public affairs, and the ability to register as a candidate, to be elected, to vote, and to take office at all levels of government arise from political involvement. Political engagement goes beyond parties, however. Through independent action, especially at the local level, and by engaging civil society groups, individuals can also get involved in some aspects of the democratic process. For political engagement, professional networks, labor unions, non-governmental organizations, and the media may all provide avenues (UN, 2005).

Zukin, et al. (2006) identify the notion of public voice in political participation practices, which are indirect attempts to influence political outcomes by debating or communicating political issues with other members of the public through different media. Political and civic knowledge are another antecedent resource that can affect public participation. As such, those with higher levels of political and civic knowledge are better able to make wise decisions about their activities. Examples of political and civic knowledge include the democratic process, information about candidates and political leaders, the ways to voice complaints, and knowledge of current events (Milner, 2002; Prior, 2007).

What is “online participation”? Despite its prominence, it remains somewhat ambiguous and ill-defined. To date, the term is not known or there is no generally accepted definition (Lutz et al., 2014). A recent study of communication and Internet research theoretical perspectives listed "online participation" as one of six global themes (Rice and Fuller, 2013). Rice and Fuller discovered that the number of articles discussing participation increased significantly in the previous decade—in reality, of the six themes listed, the topic of participants experienced the greatest interest growth. Yet several studies lack a clear understanding and definition of online participation. In fact, many studies on online participation suffer from a lack of a clear conceptual and theoretical foundation (Hoffman, 2012). In a recent study of the notion of online political participation, Gadras and Greffet note how tough it is “to distinguish between participating, discussing, engaging and other activities such as reading, particularly, but not specifically, in an online context.” (Gadras and Greffet, 2013).

Lutz et al., (2014), although does not expressly define the concept of online

participation, propose three dimensions as critical to this concept: (1) The *creative* dimension: stating that online participant is associated with the creation and sharing of contents on the internet; (2) The *social* dimension: states that creation and sharing of activities are commonly embedded in social group or community; (3) The *motivational* dimension: states that online participation is commonly associated with the quest of a social purpose. They further state that the notion of online participation is generated from motivation to affect others, to impact or change the status quo, even if in a minor way.

Zukin, et al. (2006) define political participation as “activity that has the intent or effect of influencing government action – either directly by affecting the making or implementation of public policy, or indirectly by influencing the selection of people who make those policies” through activities such as voting, contributing to political parties, contacting officials and membership in political parties are all separate, observable types of political involvement (Putnam, 2000). Lutz et al., (2014) propose the following definition of the “online participation” that covers all the above-mentioned dimensions: “Online participation is the creation and sharing of content on the Internet addressed at a specific audience and driven by a social purpose.” He further elaborates that not all three elaborated dimensions are necessarily equal in all forms of online participation. Users can participate online to e-mail a petition to a politician, which, at first glance, means a mere act of interpersonal communication, but is certainly driven by a social purpose. Or creating crowdsourced art, may not follow an instantly evident social purpose, but engages a social audience in an obviously creative act. Lastly, managing a blog on feminist culture may not meet a very clearly defined audience, yet constitutes a both creative and purpose-driven use of the Internet (Lutz et al., 2014).

An illustrative example of the impact of integrating digital instruments in political and civic knowledge advancement has been in the utilization of political websites to advise voters and encourage engagement (Owen and Davis, 2008).

Over the past years, numerous studies have shown that socio–demographic variables affect individuals’ ability to access the Internet and use online media (van Dijk, 2006; Hargittai and Hinnant, 2008; van Deursen and van Dijk, 2010; Zillien and Hargittai, 2009). Whereas these findings suggest that online participation can have important social impacts, recent studies also indicate that the effect of socio–demographic antecedents on online participation may actually differ by the form of participation under observation (Blank, 2013; Hoffmann, et al., 2014; van Deursen, et al., 2014). In other words, The ‘participation divide’ may vary in width and shape on the basis of the social domain of participation. (Lutz et al., 2014).

As communication technologies further developed, political websites began to utilize social media and other interactive means to encourage a variety of political participation activities. Scholars find, however, that only “partisans” commonly visit political websites, and as such, little effort is done on campaign websites to encourage “uncommitted voters” toward higher levels of political participation (Bimber and Davis, 2003; Foot and Schneider, 2006).

The measurement of public participation has been of particular interest to social, political science, communications, and democracy scholars. Some key studies have considerably contributed to the comprehension of mass participation that led to sophisticated models. Milbrath’s (1965) seminal framework provided a set of parameters through which scholars could examine political participation. This framework marked

political participation as a pyramid of activity in which the public move from lower levels (of learning about a candidate, voting) to higher levels of more involved activities (volunteering for a campaign or running for office). Milbrath was one of the first scholars to use a classified model of measured political participation to connect participation with individual and external characteristics, such as socioeconomic status and life experiences (Riel, 2012a).

Four distinct categories of political activity were established by Verba and Nie (1972) in which the public could engage: “voting, election campaign activity, contacting public officials, and cooperative activity”. In their research, they confirmed the relationship between socioeconomic status to political participation with a high correlation. An individual’s race and community size were also identified to be factors that determine participation. Conway’s work on political participation affirmed the same high correlation of socioeconomic and life experience patterns with political and civic participation, additionally finding that mass media use decreases trust in community organizations and reduces social interaction within communities (Conway’s, 1985).

Putnam’s well-known analysis on social capital examined the behaviors of demographic groups and their activities in a variety of participation domains. Following finding a great decline in levels of participation in all domains from 1950 to 1990, such as in levels of membership in social organizations, Putnam characterizes this drop-in activity to information and communication technologies that have individualized the American public and have encouraged an attitude of isolation, particularly via broadcast television (Putnam, 2000).

Acknowledging the rise of the internet as a medium for social communication and

organization, Katz and Rice found some implications of public participation in the age of the Internet and its use on different social institutions. They found that the Internet is not necessarily a tool that promotes social isolation, but instead encourages the development of new forms of communities (Katz and Rice, 2002).

A review of the literature and history of public participation reveals that participation has been faced with changes in form, tools, and activities. Some activities have been lessened and some new forms of participation have emerged after the introduction of information and communication technologies.

3. The Context of Afghanistan: Digital Divide and Public Participation

The Afghan people have been suffering from ethnic violence, turmoil, insecurity, and the horrors of terrorism and extremism for over four decades. The outcome of the Bonn Conference provided Afghanistan with unique historical opportunity for transitioning to democracy and bringing political and social change. Peacebuilding, democratization, and state-building processes were launched under the sponsorship of the United Nations. An unparalleled stream of aid into the region, with a serious international focus on Afghanistan, allowed the NGOs and of course, the government of Afghanistan to fund reconstruction projects to bring the country out of the ashes of war.

Afghanistan has made progress in the post-2001 implementation of the peace agenda set out in the Bonn Agreement. Yet in managing the social divisions, ethnic and linguistic problems that affect the young generation in the country, Afghanistan faces more subtle challenges. Now, at the end of the process of democratic transition, Afghanistan has begun a phase of democratic consolidation in which it is expected that the Afghan government

and civil society will concentrate on democratic and political growth and successful nation-building based on the popular values set out in the Constitution. The government needs a policy change towards its social and political participation of the population, which can play a vital role in the country's political growth and a successful social transition from present ethnicity-centered politics to a more national one.

Some scholars have sorted out types of political participation in two forms of institutionalized and non-institutionalized. Whereas institutionalized participation is specifically connected to acts with a direct effect on the institutional and electoral systems, non-institutionalized forms of participation have an indirect effect on the policy-making process. The latter form may include, for instance, participation in demonstrations, signing petitions, boycotting goods, disobedience, hunger strikes, etc. Observed realities indicate that in many countries, institutionalized forms of political participation have been diminishing, but non-institutionalized forms have begun to gain more importance in comparison. This can be viewed as an indication that while the democratic system is still accepted by people, they have become more critical of how democracy actually operates. In developing countries with poor and ineffective institutions, non-institutionalized modes of political engagement are observable in more severe ways and forms (Marien, 2010).

In post-conflict states, including Afghanistan where the national government is largely made ineffective, non-institutionalized forms of political involvement are typically triggered by the slow pace of institutionalization or the inefficiency of existing political and social institutions. Institutions in these countries fail to integrate the major interests of different social and political classes and lack the capacity to explicitly

accommodate the interests of newly mobilized groups (Qasim Wafayezada, 2015).

In terms of Digital divide, Afghanistan is one of the countries with the highest gap and lowest internet penetration rate of only 20%, as of January 2020 (ATRA, 2020). There is a gap between the urban population and rural population as well. Despite all the security and geographical challenges faced by the players of ICT, significant positive changes have been made in this sector.

Since 2001, Afghanistan has experienced immense growth and expansion in its information and communication technology (ICT) sector when it revamped its stance on promoting wireless connectivity, the rollout of optical fiber in and around the Country, and the expansion of internet usage. There has also been enormous work done to enhance several legal and regulatory frameworks geared at liberalizing the ICT sectors in order to promote competition and stimulate sectoral growth. Major stakeholders, such as Internet Service Providers (ISPs) are now providing seamless last-mile services to their customers. The Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) are building their own infrastructures, and the international voice gateway opened to each Operator. These developments happened in tandem with the government's pronouncement, under the auspices of the Ministry of ICT and development partners, to develop a modern Telecommunications and Internet Sector Policy, which was then published in October 2002. That policy framework led to the foundation for a more transparent, private sector-led competition. This initiative paid off. As of 2009, there were more than 10.4 million mobile subscribers, a 300-fold increase in seven years with more than \$1.2 billion invested in the sector (Benson, 2021).

Eighteen years since the adoption of the country's Telecommunications and Internet Sector policy in 2002, an assessment of the telecommunications sector shows that there

has been an uptick, but encouraging growth in the sector, especially with Broadband development. On a positive note, as of the first quarter of 2020, despite the Broadband sector is still at an early stage of development and penetration remains relatively low compared to other countries in the region, the Broadband sector is highly competitive, with five operators along with 62 registered Internet service providers (as of 2018) providing fixed and mobile Broadband connectivity to subscribers. Unlike the low subscription rate of fixed Broadband in the country as the result of limited availability and high costs, mobile Broadband on the other hand is thriving exponentially (ATRA, 2020).

Amidst the enormous gains achieved so far in the sector, the price of Broadband internet is relatively high for the ordinary Afghan (ITU Data, 2019). There are many factors that are driving the price hike - amongst them being the high overhead and operational cost, high taxes on ICT goods and services, security ramifications, stringent and bureaucratic Right of Way (RoW) procedures. The government needs to collaborate with the private sector to address these concerns. Additionally, the government recognizes that the lack of a comprehensive policy framework via a national Broadband policy to address policy and regulatory concern is hampering the growth of the sector (Benson, 2021).

Research Question

The following primary research question is asked to guide this study: **To what degree does the digital divide influence public participation?**

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. Theoretical Framework of the Study

The theoretical framework of the thesis is based on the direct relationships between the independent variables: internet access, internet use, digital literacy, technology perceived benefit and dependent variable; social participation, political participation. Social and economic variables (age, gender, education, and income) are considered as the controlling variables. Figure 5 illustrates the proposed theoretical framework and the relationships between variables.

Figure 5. A Theoretical Model of internet access, internet use, digital literacy, and perceived benefit on social and political participation

I have constructed the framework of this study focusing on two major fields. Firstly, I have conducted a systematic analysis of previous studies on “participation” in social and

political disciplines and identified two major domains as the main focus of this study. Secondly, in order to obtain an understanding of the evolving relationship between digital divide and public participation, the existing literature from information and communications technology (ICT) field, education discipline (for assessing the digital literacy), and theoretical works of scholars were also reviewed.

2. Theoretical Underpinning of the Model

2.1. Theories related to Digital Divide

This study is mainly based on four important theories, namely Technology Acceptance Model, Technology Determinism Theory, Diffusion of Innovation Theory, and Social Exclusion Theory.

Smith and Marx (1996) argued that the digital divide debate is originally considered as an aspect of Technological Determinism Theory (TDT). It is a technology-based theory of social change; in which, the technology – technical development – is perceived as the main driver and principal determinant of human relations, culture, and social structure, whereas the social factors are considered secondary.

Taking the fact that not all changes are as a result of technology, the need for another approach to explain the motives why some groups of people tend to adopt novel technologies, and some do not, was sensed. Everett Rogers (2003) supporting the Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT), argues that the emergence of technology itself is not the only reason which motivates the people to adopt it ‘en mass’. The mentioned theory seeks to find out why, where, and to what quality the emerging technologies spread.

He, contrary to technological determinists, goes beyond and proposes three other elements that foster the spread of technology: the innovative technology itself, communication channel, first adopters, first majority, and late majority. Rogers' arguments are very close to that of Tichenor who developed the knowledge gap hypothesis (Donohue and Olien, 1970; Everett Rogers, 2003). The majority of scholars, supporting this hypothesis, propose that during the study of the digital divide, both access and use should be considered equally (Srinuan, 2012).

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) which was introduced in 1986, explains the main factors that provoke users to accept technology the acceptance of information technology by its users (Davis, 1989). According to the model, two beliefs affect the user's decision for accepting the newly introduced technology, namely: "Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use."

Since the 'lack of physical infrastructure as the primary cause of digital divide' has been studied in earlier literature in Afghanistan, this work in addition to internet access, considers the internet use, digital literacy and perceived benefit adapted from the Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) as the main subjects of its study under digital divide theme.

The "theory of uses and gratifications" suggests that media choice and exposure fulfill the social and psychological needs of people for gratification (E. Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch, 1973, 1974). This approach describes why people are committed and goal-oriented internet users; they choose various Internet activities to satisfy their motives (Ruggiero, 2000). For example, people use the internet for fun and amusement to satisfy their leisure motivation, to find information for learning new information on the Internet

to fulfill their personal development purposes, and to interact with friends on social media in order to satisfy their belong needs (van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014). Therefore, the uses and gratifications theory support the classification of Internet usage types developed from the most common contemporary Internet activities.

2.1. Social Exclusion Theory: a public participation theory

Social exclusion theory, which is a multidimensional concept that goes beyond material poverty and associates social exclusion with exclusion from access to services and power structures, social participation, cultural and structural processes, opportunities to build human capital, is the principal conceptual framework for digital divide in the intra city level. In the past, social exclusion has been associated with low income, poor job skills, unemployment, poor housing and neighborhoods that lack security with poor family structures (Social Exclusion Unit, 1998). Levitas (1998) defined social exclusion within the broader dialogue of moral, social integration and redistribution discourses that is concerned with poverty, inequality, and structural oppression. Miliband (2006) extended it to social inequality as concentrated and deep exclusion. He believes, concentrated exclusion can occur as a result of geographic concentration of disadvantages, on the other hand deep exclusion is as a result of disadvantages on multiple levels of structural oppression that is interconnected to various factors. According to Duffy (1995), those who are excluded socially are unable to participate effectively in social, political, economic and cultural life due to some characteristic distinctions from the mainstream society, and are deprived in resources and opportunities resulting from structural oppression linked to being part of certain geographical location, socio-economic status,

race, language and so on.

In this study, I look at digital divide as a gap between those who have broadband access, digital literacy, use the internet and have motivation and those who do not. Considering the above definitions, the digital divide is an outcome and indicator of exclusion. Nevertheless, I also examine it as a result of inequality in many socio-economic factors which results in lack of access and utilization of technology. Basically, the digital divide represents disparity in access to technology which can enhance the quality of life of the people. Those groups of people, who do not have accessibility to technology are digitally excluded and are prohibited from broader access to resources and opportunities in society, compared to those who have access and utilize technological means. As per the Sen's capabilities concepts, digital technology has influential relevance: lacking in broadband and internet may lead to other exclusions such as inability to find or apply for a job online, access information online, inability to complete homework assignments effectively, depriving from access to online public services and failing to locate vital health information (Sen's, 1995). Majority of the digitally excluded groups are more probable to be less educated with less well-paid jobs, income and education and are disconnected from digital usage (Foley et al., 2003).

3. Dependent Variables of Public Participation

In this section, social participation and political participation, as two domains of public participation, being examined in this thesis, will be further elaborated.

Similar to digital divide, public participation has also been studied thoroughly by researchers and social science scholars. Simply put, public participation is the

engagement of the public in civic, political, and social activities. On a general term, public participation is comprised of the activities carried out for socialization, influencing people or bringing about social and political changes, such as, effecting social reforms through demonstrations or using petition right to change certain policy decisions (Riel, 2012a).

Public participation is transforming significantly in the 21st century, as compared to other socio-economic movements. These transformation trends have led to the emergence of new paradigms and novel forms of participation (Innes and Booher, 2004). Five stages of the public participation process have been established by the International Association for Public Participation (IAPP), which facilitates public participation in government decision-making around the globe: inform, consult, engage, collaborate and empower. (Najimi, 2018).

As research on mass participation expanded, scholars have described other preconditions and antecedent skills in greater detail that affect the capacity and interest of an individual in mass participation. These preconditions and skills include access to information technology, influence, political and civic knowledge, information exposure, literacy, and communication skills.

Social participation domain of participation is an important aspect regarding the research of mass participation, even though some scholars argue that political participation might be more important for the democratic health (Zukin, et al., 2006).

Zukin, et al. (2006) define political participation as “activity that has the intent or effect of influencing government action – either directly by affecting the making or implementation of public policy, or indirectly by influencing the selection of people who make those policies” through activities such as voting, contributing to political parties,

contacting officials and membership in political parties are all separate, observable types of political involvement (Putnam, 2000).

4. Independent Variables of Digital Divide

In this study, four key dimensions of digital divide are used as independent variables: internet access, internet use, digital literacy, and perceived benefit.

In order to use modern technology, a person should first be motivated to use it. When adequate motivation is created, one should be able to obtain physical access to a digital device (such as a computer or smartphone), the Internet or another digital medium. In addition, material resources are required to continue utilizing technology consisting of peripheral equipment, software, ink, paper, subscriptions, etc. Having physical and material access does not necessarily lead to the appropriation of technology, as one should first develop necessary skills for the use of the medium. The further these skills are developed; the more appropriate use will be made of the technology (J. A. G. M. Van Dijk, 2012).

4.1. Independent Variable: Internet Access

The vast majority of digital divide research is devoted to the study of physical access divide to personal computers and the Internet between demographic categories that are: income, education, age, gender, and ethnicity. Van Dijk studied differential access and characteristics of individuals to information and computing technology (ICTs) and related them to *personal categorical inequality* factors as below: “age (young/old); gender (male/female); race/ethnicity (majority/minority); Intelligence (high/low); personality (extravert/introvert; self-confident/not self-confident); health (abled/disabled).

The same applies to the following positional categorical inequalities: Labor position (entrepreneurs or workers; management/employees; employed /unemployed); education (high/low); household (family/single person); nation (developed/developing)” (J. A. G. M. Van Dijk, 2012). Concerning the gender and age, findings suggest that women and elderly people are decreasingly likely to use ICT facilities than men and youth (Wasserman & Richmond-Abbott, 2005; Antonio & Tuffley, 2014; Okunola et al., 2017; Srinuan, 2012).

The socio-demographic variables on the usage of ICT are also considered. For instance, interviewees with better education, job, and higher income have reported greater access to digital facilities, which in turn leads to an increased level of previous internet experience (Okunola et al., 2017; Srinuan, 2012). The best way would be training young members of the community about the benefits of ICTs who, in turn, can raise awareness for others (Srinuan, 2012, Babu et al., 2012, Upadhyaya, 2019).

4.2. Independent Variable: Internet Use

Having sufficient motivation, physical access, and skills to apply digital media are necessary but not sufficient conditions of actual use, because digital use has its own factors and determinants (J. A. G. M. Van Dijk, 2012).

There are numerous studies that illustrate how internet use depends on different biological, economic, social, or organizational factors in the general population. Age is adversely linked to internet usage, but higher education, higher income, having a career, marital status are correlated with higher internet use. (Scholz et al., 2017). As for the gender gap, which is getting closer in most of the developed countries but still women

use the internet lesser than men for different reasons (Robinson et al., 2015; Hargittai, 2006)

Van Dijk (2012) states that digital use as a dependent factor can be measured in four ways: “usage time and frequency; number and diversity of usage applications; broadband or narrowband use; more or less active or creative use.”

4.3. Independent Variable: Digital Literacy

Since public participation has taken on a new form as a result of utilization of information technology, the skills and expertise needed for mass participation have also changed. Digital literacy, the ability to effectively use digitally networked tools to find, evaluate, create, share, and synthesize electronic information, is regularly regarded by education and literary scholars as a rising skill set for the general public. As a result, digital inclusion policies have been developed in many countries to promote internet skills of individuals (Alexander J.A.M. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2015).

Literacy and communication abilities have been related to greater levels of public participation. It can be basically defined as the familiarity or ability to efficiently use electronic tools internet-based device to find information, create contents, disseminate, and share the information with others (Wilhelm, 2000).

Van Deursen and van Dijk presented six types of internet skills and several types of measurements. The six types of internet skills are: operational skills, formal skills, informal skills, communication skills, content-creation skills and strategic skills (A. J.A.M. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2010; Alexander J.A.M. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2015; Van Dijk, 2012). Digital literacy scholars propose that a digitally literate person should

not only be aware how to operate the technology yet should also understand the social setting under which information is created and the boundaries of the media in which information is presented (Gee, 2008; Lankshear & Knobel, 2006; Kress, 2003). In the light of this, measures of digital literacy should not only contain mastery of discrete technological abilities, but also a broader knowledge of the origins and bias of information (Riel, 2012a).

4.2. Independent Variable: Perceived Benefit

The desire to have a device and to be linked to the Internet comes prior to physical access. The access to digital means such as computers and the internet starts with a motivation and a positive attitude for using these means. Of course, the outcomes of using digital media are the main objective of the process. As Van Dijk, people use technology and digital means in hope to find the benefits of these technologies. (Alexander & van Dijk, 2017).

The factors that explain motivational access are social or cultural as well as mental or psychological in essence. As Katz and Rice argue that "the Internet has no attraction for low-income and low-educated individuals" (Katz and Rice, 2002).

5. Hypotheses

The author has proposed hypotheses that were made in the theoretical framework (Figure 5.) The following hypotheses were developed to be tested in this thesis, to examine the influence of digital divide on various domains of public participation:

H₁: There is a positive correlation between internet access and political participation.

H₂: There is a positive correlation between internet access and social participation.

H₃: There is a positive correlation between internet use and social participation.

H₄: There is a positive correlation between internet use and political participation.

H₅: Digital literacy is correlated the most with a higher level of political participation compared to social participation.

H₆: Digital literacy has the strongest positive influence on social participation when compared to social-economic status (SES) variables.

H₇: Digital literacy has the strongest positive influence on social participation when compared to social-economic status (SES) variables.

H₈: Perceived Benefit is correlated the most with a higher level of political participation compared to social participation.

H₉: Digital divide has the strongest positive influence on public participation when compared to social-economic status (SES) as control variable.

H₁₀: Lower level of digital divide leads to higher level of public participation.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1. Research Setting and Population

As for the sampling, the scope and target population of this study is Kabul Province with 4.43 million residents (NSIA, 2020). It means that with a confidence level of 95% and real value of $\pm 5\%$, a minimum of 354 samples are needed to meet the desired statistical constraints. As for the country (Afghanistan) with a population of 38.9 million (NSIA, 2020), with 99% confidence level and $\pm 5\%$ real value, minimum 666 samples are required to have a good representation of the population in our research.

2. Research Design

To obtain accurate results of the public's perception, the participants must be selected randomly. The word "random" is very important in citizen-based survey research. If a sample is selected randomly, every individual in the population has an equal opportunity of being chosen. The reason that randomness is so crucial is that a random selection is possibly to be fairly representative of the whole population from which it was selected. When a sample of people is chosen randomly and then asked questions, we can be fairly sure that the opinions expressed will be close to the entire population.

One of the challenges of this research is that there is no exact list of the entire Kabul population (or any address or telephone numbers book) in order to perform a probabilistic random sampling. The full list of the population of Kabul Province is not available in any source. When there is no list, according to scholars, the researchers can still keep randomness of the sample.

In this research, since the list of the entire population was not accessible to draw sample; therefore, the city is divided into various areas called as Primary Sampling Units (PSUs). On a regular basis, the researcher has to divide each PSU into smaller regions and sub-divide those smaller regions into city blocks or rural areas and then select people from those final blocks or areas randomly.

As illustrated in Figure 6, I use a two-stage stratified random sampling as well as purposive sampling approach simultaneously intended to reach out and include all sectors of the population. Area sampling under the stratified random sampling was utilized to find out the areas of study, known as “enumeration areas.” For the first stage, the whole province was divided into 22 districts; later on, 10 districts were chosen randomly as study areas. The first stage of the sampling results in geographic “clusters.” In these clusters, there are sets of units (usually households) that are closely located geographically that minimizes the cost of data collection, which increases sampling error because of the homogeneity of units within clusters that is called clustering effect (UNSD, 2005b). For the second stage, it was intended to perform dwelling, household, and individual sampling within clusters; however, the author chose to conduct purposive sampling technique that is less time-consuming and more cost-efficient. This technique has also been used in recent researches on internet use and digital surveys as well (Reddick et al., 2020; Akombwa & Tembo, 2020; Haines, 2020; Miranda et al., 2013). In purposive non-random sampling, the researcher chose people who are interested in providing the appropriate information from their own knowledge and experience pertaining to the issue under investigation (Bernard, 2002). In this stage, the author attempted to have the representation of participants from different socio-economic: age,

gender and educational statuses, income groups based on their location, so that to reflect the diverse experiences and perceptions throughout Kabul Province.

Figure 6. Sampling Plan: Sources of Survey Questionnaire Respondents

The aim was to access a cross-section of the population from all districts of the province. Data were collected using intercept surveying through respondents completing the paper-based survey at universities, libraries, community centers, mosques etc. or by surveyors with tablets or smartphones and collecting the data face-to-face.

This work is a quantitative study where primary data is used. The required primary data was collected from a sample of approximately (N=354) drawn out of 4 million citizens residing in the capital, Kabul. The unit of analysis in this study is “individual.” Subsequently, the collected data was analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) v26.0 to analyze correlations between variables in the data. The dependent variables are the domains “public participation” while “digital divide”

dimensions are considered as the independent variables anticipated to have impacts on the dependent variable.

3. Strategy of Tests

To test the hypotheses in this study, I used a series of ordinary least-squares regressions (OLS) and Pearson's R correlations to define the strength and direction of the effect of digital divide on the various domains of public participation. These statistical procedures use data from the survey that was used to provide data on respondent level of digital divide which was measured by 22 indicators. In addition, the survey also provides data on participants level of public participation in two domains, that include, social participation, and political participation. In addition to the above, Point-biserial Correlation was conducted to find the correlation between nominal variables of age, gender, education and income, and dependent and independent variables.

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using IBM AMOS was also conducted to test the data for biasedness. The researcher checked the "biasedness" through performing a bootstrap using the default values set by AMOS (200 number of bootstrap samples and 90% Bias-correlated confidence level).

4. Operationalization and Measurement of Variables

For over two decades the digital divide has become a bottleneck for global sustainable development, and there have been a lot of studies in terms of measuring the digital divide and mass participation using various measurements scales.

To obtain empirical data for this work, I developed a nationally representative survey

questionnaire comprised of 32 indicators to compare levels of digital divide to public participation activities. Benefiting from the existing rich literature on digital divide, especially from the international organization such as, International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and OECD, I utilized a set of indicators with which I could test my hypotheses. As such, I developed a number of survey indicators that are linked to the four dimensions of digital divide that I discussed in Chapter 1 and 2: internet access, internet use, digital literacy, and perceived benefit. 22 separate indicators related to digital divide were included in the survey. Respondents also answered 12 questions on their demographic and background information. Each of the indicators being used to measure both dependent and independent variables is detailed in Appendix I.

Similar to digital divide, I developed survey questions in order to measure respondents' level of public participation in two domains. The indicators used in most of the previous research were requiring dichotomous responses (Yes or No); however, in order to know the exact level of respondents' participation in various social and political activities, I have preferred to use the Likert scale of 1 to 5. The numeric scores represented (1) as Strongly Disagree to (5) as Strongly Agree on 10 mass participation activities and perceptions within two domains.

Regarding Internet Access (Cronbach's α : .834), respondents were asked about their level of access to internet and broadband services at home, job or education place, the speed of internet and lastly the price and affordability to access internet. The variable was measured using a 5-point scale (ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree). Respondents were asked about their access to the internet, using 4 survey items.

Pertaining to internet use (Cronbach α : .872), respondents were asked about the

frequency they use the internet or perform online activities. The items used to measure internet usage are consist of use online social media or networking sites (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, ...), access to online to information (such as health, government info...), use a mobile phone to connect to the Internet, and share information, photos, and videos online. The variable was measured using a 5-point scale (ranging from Never to All the time). Respondents were asked about their level of internet use using 4 survey items.

Related to digital literacy (Cronbach α : .945), respondents were asked about how capable and skillful are they in the following items related to technology and the internet: using computer to do basic things, install drivers or software on a new PC, save information from the internet to a PC, create or edit documents, create and edit videos, online privacy and information security, identify fake information, and lastly send or receive emails. The variable was measured using a 5-point scale (ranging from Not skillful at all to very skillful). Respondents were asked about their digital literacy using 4 survey items.

Perceived Benefit (Cronbach α : .923) was measured using a 5-point scale (ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree). Respondents were asked about their feelings and life experience about the internet, using 6 survey items.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Sample Characteristics

Variable	Group	<i>n</i> Frequency	% Percentage
Gender	Female	194	54.8%
	Male	160	45.2%
Age	18-24	136	38.4%
	25-34	110	31.1%
	35-44	45	12.7%
	45-54	33	9.3%
	55 or above	30	8.5%
Marital Status	Single	188	53.1%
	Married	166	46.9%
Income	20,000 AFS or below	155	43.8%
	20,000 - 50,000 AFS	126	35.6%
	50,000 - 100,000 AFS	48	13.6%
	100,000 - 150,000 AFS	14	4.0%
	150,000 - 200,000 AFS	5	1.4%
	200,000 AFS or above	6	1.7%
Education	No official education	32	9.0%
	Primary	22	6.2%
	Secondary	50	14.1%
	Undergraduate	202	57.1%
	Graduate	48	13.6%
Employment Status	Looking for Job	133	37.6%
	Civil Service/Public Service	66	18.6%
	Education/Teaching	25	7.1%
	Trading/Business	41	11.6%
	Medical/Health	18	5.1%
	Computer/ICT	11	3.1%
	Banking/Insurance	6	1.7%
	Other Jobs ...	54	15.3%
English Language Competency	Very Bad	70	19.8%
	Elementary	69	19.5%
	Intermediate	92	26.0%
	Upper-intermediate	87	24.6%
	Advanced	36	10.2%

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The survey demonstrates that majority of the survey respondents were those in age group between 18 to 24 years, who accounted for 38.4% of the total respondents, followed by those between 25 and 34 years who accounted for 31.1%, whereas 12.7% of the respondents had age between 35 to 44 years, and respondents between the age of 45 to 54 and above 55 years registered 9.3% and 8.5% of total respondents respectively.

In terms of employment status, majority of the respondents are categorized under “Looking for Job - jobless” at 37.6%, followed by civil servants who comprised 18.6 percent of the sample, respondents engaged in private businesses registered 11.6%, while respondents working in the education and teaching, medical, computer and ICT, and banking are accounted for 7.1%, 5.1% and 3.1% respectively. “Other jobs” comprise 15.3% of the respondents. In terms of education level, majority of the respondents were undergraduates (57.1%), followed by respondents with secondary school education at 14.1%, graduates accounted for 13.6% of respondents while those without any education certificate and those with primary school education registered 9.0% and 6.2% of the total respondents, respectively.

2. Missing Value Analysis

The questionnaire was checked by the listwise deletion method of Cronbach’s Alpha calculation for missing values using SPSS and the results show that all the cases are valid, and no participant was excluded. It is because the survey used “Must fill the form option” on an online form that was used by surveyor carrying smart phone and tablets. Additionally, since the type of data collection was intercept surveying, therefore the questionnaire was checked by the surveyor for any missing data.

3. Descriptive Statistics

When conducting research, calculating descriptive statistics is a critical first step that should always be performed before attempting inferential statistical comparisons. Descriptive statistics are a set of short descriptive coefficients that summarize a data set, which can be a representation of the whole population or a sample of it. Descriptive statistics are subdivided into measures of central tendency and measures of variability (spread). Central tendency measures include the mean, median, and mode, while variability measures include standard deviation, variance, minimum and maximum variables, kurtosis, and skewness. In short, descriptive statistics help define and understand the features of a specific data set by providing short summaries about the sample and how the data is measured. Descriptive statistics enable researchers to assess specific populations in a more manageable way because they condense data into a simpler summary (Kaur and Yellapu, 2018).

Descriptive Statistics

Constructs	N Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean Statistic Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness Statistic	Kurtosis Statistic
<i>Independent Variables</i>							
Internet Access	354	1.00	5.00	3.1264	1.17505	.113	-1.195
Internet Use	354	1.00	5.00	3.7684	1.16564	-1.139	.110
Digital Literacy	354	1.00	5.00	3.2581	1.26607	-.533	-1.080
Perceived Benefit	354	1.00	5.00	4.0042	1.03468	-1.603	1.740
<i>Dependent Variables</i>							
Social Participation	354	1.00	5.00	2.7241	1.04848	-.096	-.896
Political Participation	354	1.00	4.86	2.6344	1.33409	.469	-1.093
Valid N (listwise)	354						

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Descriptive statistics for all the dependent and independent variables: internet access, internet use, digital literacy, motivation, social participation, and political participation were computed. The results of this study demonstrate that digital divide dimensions such as access and use are the means that foster mass participation while digital literacy is a prerequisite skill for efficient participation in society. The data show that the digital divide among female is more widened than men. A similar case applies to age groups. The comparisons of means indicate that youth have more internet access, use and digital literacy in compared to older people. This indicates that men and youth have more social and political engagement and influence in the society more than female and old people, as they enjoy higher levels of technology use. These facts demonstrate that there is a serious need for initiatives from the government, private sector, and other stakeholders toward mitigating the gender digital gap and increasing adult digital literacy programs in society. It is likely that the internet usage and literacy skills among certain groups and their absence in others will flow the resources and connections toward those that enjoy this advantage. This could affect a shift in society, power, or politics in the near future.

The values for skewness and kurtosis between -2 and +2 are considered acceptable in order to prove normal univariate distribution (George & Mallery, 2010). Hair et al. (2010) claimed that data is considered to be normal if skewness is between -2 to +2 and kurtosis is between -7 to +7.

3.1. Summary of the Statistical Findings

In this section, I give a snapshot of the current levels of digital divide of Kabul residents and illustrate how often do they engage in public participation activities. Using data collected from the people that belong to different groups, I highlight differences in digital divide dimensions and mass participation domains within five key demographics: gender, age, education, income level and English proficiency. Differences of means between various groups are examined with one-way ANOVA tests and independent samples t-tests.

3.1.1. *High perceived benefit & internet use, minimum internet access & digital literacy*

By comparing the mean scores of the digital divide and public participation domains, I found that people generally scored 3 in digital divide domains that include *internet access* with mean scores (at home: 3.43; access outside home: 3.15; internet speed: 2.99 and affordability: 2.68); *internet use* with mean scores (online social media use: 3.84; online information: 3.56; using mobile phone to connect to internet: 4.1; share information 3.55).

Figure 7 demonstrates the differences in mean scores of each of the four domains of the digital divide and public participation.

Figure 7. Mean Scores for Digital Divide and Public Participation Domains (Based on mean scale score; total $n = 354$)

Lower score in the internet access domain is due to minimum *affordability* to access the internet using monthly prepaid bundles (2.68) in a smartphone as well as the *low speed* of the internet (2.99).

3.1.2. Men enjoy narrowed digital divide and higher levels of public participation

Figure 8 demonstrates the differences in digital divide and public participation domains (measured by the omnibus adjusted summary scale) which are separated by gender. Two independent sample t-tests were conducted to find out the distinctions in mean scores between the two genders. The conclusion of the first test is that the population mean of the digital divide for female participants is the same as the population of the digital divide for male participants as the two-tailed significant level was not $<.005$.

Thus, we can conclude that we are not certain whether the digital divide is widened among female population or not and the same case applies to male population. So, there is no gender difference in the digital divide in our data.

Figure 8. Digital Divide and Public Participation by Gender
(Based on mean scale score; total $n = 354$)

The conclusion for the second test is that the population mean of the public participation for female participants is different than the population of the public participation for male participants as the two-tailed test was significant at the level $<.005$. So, we can conclude that we can be certain that the public participation level among female population is lower in compared to male population.

Means Report

Gender	Internet Access	Internet Use	Digital Literacy	Perceived Benefit	Social Participation	Political Participation
0 Female	3.2887	3.6314	3.0593	4.0430	2.5241	2.5493
1 Male	2.9297	3.9344	3.4992	3.9573	2.9667	2.7375
Total	3.1264	3.7684	3.2581	4.0042	2.7241	2.6344

Table 3.

Mean Scores for digital divide and participation dimensions among male and female

3.1.3. The digital divide is widened among elderly in compared to youth

Young generation has been popularly known as the “digital natives” or “net-generation” and are generally regarded to have lower levels of digital divide in compared to elderly. Differences in the mean scores among different age groups reveal a downward trend in digital divide mean scores as age increases.

Figure 9 demonstrates this observation, with younger age groups showing higher mean scores of digital divide dimensions than those with older ages.

Figure 9.

Mean Scores for digital divide dimensions among youth and elderly ($n = 354$)

Differences in the mean scores among different age groups in public participation mean scores also show the same case as above. Figure 9 demonstrates this observation, with younger age groups showing higher mean scores of social and political participations than those with older ages.

Figure 10.

Mean Scores for public participation domains among youth and elderly ($n = 354$)

To test the significant differences between mean digital divide and public participation scores by age group, I utilized a one-way ANOVA test ($F = 105.9$; $p < .000$) on digital divide and another test ($F = 23.0$; $p < .000$) on public participation grouped by age factor.

3.1.4. Level of education on digital divide and public participation

Figures 11 and 12 illustrate the differences in the divide and public participation domains separated by education level, which reveals an upward trend in digital divide mean scores as the education level increases.

Figure 11 demonstrates this observation, with participants having master's or bachelor's degree show higher mean scores of digital divide dimensions than those without any official education certificates.

Figure 11. Digital divide difference means between education Levels

Differences in the mean scores among different age groups in public participation mean scores also show the same case as above, being illustrated in below figure.

Figure 12. Public Participation difference means between education levels

To test the significant differences between mean digital divide and public participation scores by education levels, I utilized a one-way ANOVA test ($F = 107.0$; $p < .000$) on digital divide and another test ($F = 25.0$; $p < .000$) on public participation grouped by education level factor.

3.1.5. Level of income on digital divide and public participation

The differences in the divide and public participation domains separated by income level were also calculated and the results reveal different scores where we cannot conclude that people with higher levels of income have better digital access, use and literacy to use the internet and digital means. Figure 13 demonstrates this observation,

Figure 13. Digital divide difference means between income levels

Referring to figure 14, the above case applies to public participation as well.

Figure 14. Public Participation difference means between income levels

To test the significant differences between mean digital divide and public participation scores by income levels, I utilized a one-way ANOVA test ($F = 20.4$; $p < .000$) on digital divide and another test ($F = 10.2$; $p < .000$) on public participation grouped by income level factor.

4. Reliability and Validity Analysis

4.1. Reliability Analysis

Analyzing the Reliability of this Research, the reliability indicates the prevailing level of consistency among respondents (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010). A reliability analysis utilizing Cronbach's Alpha was performed to evaluate the reliability of the predictor variables. According to Nunnally, the generally agreed upon lower limit for Cronbach's α is 0.70 (1978). Moreover, Cronbach's Alpha coefficients were calculated for each multi-item predictor variable as well.

The statistical results of the Reliability Analysis test are mentioned below:

Reliability Statistics			
Constructs	Mean inter-item correlation	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
<i>Independent Variables</i>			
Internet Access	.533	.834	4
Internet Use	.601	.872	4
Digital Literacy	.606	.945	8
Perceived Benefit	.537	.923	6
<i>Dependent Variables</i>			
Social Participation	.457	.700	3
Political Participation	.576	.937	7

Table 4. Reliability Analysis Table

Julie Pallant (2016), in her book "The SPSS Survival Manual", she states that if there are less than 10 items for a variable, it is difficult to get value greater than .70; therefore,

she proposes to keep the items that are even greater than > 0.5 .

The output reveals that all the cases are valid, and no case had been excluded. If we have a look at the reliability statistics (Table 4), the Cronbach's Alpha for the questions is greater than $>.70$, which indicates high consistency among the respondents in this study.

4.2 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Factor analysis was employed to check if items load on the expected number of factors, as predicted or not. Exploratory factor analysis was performed on all questionnaire items to get actual and first-hand statistical information on the construct. The function of factor analysis is to exclude unwanted items in the questionnaire. This can be conducted in two ways, either rotated or unrotated form.

Regularly, the unrotated solutions do not give a suitable idea of the factor structure and for this reason, a researcher has to resort to the rotated solution. The rotated form does not change the overall factor structure fundamentally, however, only simplifies the interpretability of the output (Everett, 1983; Leandre R. Fabrigar et al., 1999). KMO and Bartlett's test was also included while conducting Exploratory factor analysis.

The below table presents the Rotated form of the Exploratory Factor Analysis for all the six factors including the Cronbach's Alpha for each factor:

Rotated Component Matrix^a

Items / COMPONENTS	Digital Literacy	Political Participation	Perceived Benefit	Internet Use	Internet Access	Social Participation
Digital_Literacy.4	.811					
Digital_Literacy.1	.808					
Digital_Literacy.2	.807					
Digital_Literacy.3	.797					
Digital_Literacy.7	.748					
Digital_Literacy.5	.738					
Digital_Literacy.6	.696					
Digital_Literacy.8	.695					
Political_Participation.7		.822				
Political_Participation.4		.818				
Political_Participation.6		.807				
Political_Participation.5		.788				
Political_Participation.2		.785				
Political_Participation.1		.716				
Political_Participation.3		.629				
Perceived_Benefit.4			.827			
Perceived_Benefit.2			.824			
Perceived_Benefit.5			.801			
Perceived_Benefit.3			.775			
Perceived_Benefit.1			.763			
Perceived_Benefit.6			.754			
Internet_Use.1				.687		
Internet_Use.3				.621		
Internet_Use.4				.616		
Internet_Use.2				.593		
Internet_Access.3					.788	
Internet_Access.4					.780	
Internet_Access.1					.606	
Internet_Access.2					.502	
Social_Participation.1						.817
Social_Participation.2						.688
Social_Participation.3						.621

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
 a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

Table 5.
 Rotated Exploratory Factor Analysis Table: Dependent and Independent Variables

The Exploratory Factor Analysis was performed in IBM SPSS v26.0 through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using Varimax rotation with Kaiser Normalization. To make certain that factor loadings were reported for acceptable variance in the overall model, instead of the criteria of Eigenvalue > 1 , six fixed number of factors were indicated to be extracted while the factor loading of $\pm .3$ and greater was employed.

The results of the above factor analysis for the selected items reveal that the items on this scale are held together. According to Hair and Anderson (1998), if the factor loading is above 0.6 such items is quite desirable, if the factor loading is above 0.4 then such items are acceptable. In this study, 30 scale items are greater than 0.6 factor loading and the remaining 2 items are above 0.5. In the case of many other scale items that loaded on multiple dimensions, were excluded from future analysis.

4.2.1. KMO and Bartlett's Test

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy index is a tool for determining whether factor analysis is appropriate, which ranges from 0 to 1. According to Malhotra and Dash (2007), high values (from 0.5 to 1.0) imply that factor analysis is appropriate (Malhotra and Dash, 2007). The value that is equal to or above 0.80 is considered as meritorious (Hair et al 2006).

From the table below, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy is .952 which is a sign of the perfect result of the study. The significance value (p value) is 0.000 which indicates the significance at 95% confidence level. The statistically significant Bartlett's test of sphericity reveals that sufficient correlations exist among all our variables to continue with factor analysis (Hair et al, 2006).

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.952
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	9098.394
	df	496
	Sig.	.000

Table 6. KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

4.2.2 Scree Test Criterion:

The scree test is extracted by plotting the latent roots (eigen values) against the component factor (number of factors) in their order of extraction, and the figure of the resulting curve is used to assess the cutoff point. Beginning with the first factor, the plot slopes sharply downward first and then gradually become more like a horizontal line. The point after which the curve starts to straighten out is considered to show the maximum number of factors to extract (Hair et al, 2006). In the present case, the six factors perfectly qualify for extraction.

Figure 15. Scree Plot for Factor Analysis

4.3. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Confirmatory Factor Analysis is the method to validate the items of a study with their respective factors (Netemeyer et al., 2003). This analysis provides the overall fitness of the theoretical model with respect to its factors. As such, the construct validity is the essential prerequisite for testing the theory (Carmines and Zeller, 1979); therefore, Confirmatory Factor Analysis is the right tool to measure the construct validity (Bagozzi et al, 1991). In this study, the convergent validity and discriminant validity were assessed using CFA analysis in SPSS AMOS software.

The outputs of the confirmatory factor analysis indicate that the data employed in this study do fit the model well. This is as per the values of the overall CFA fit indices which fall either in the acceptable range of values or are very close to the cut-off criteria.

CMIN/DF=2.56/445 (< 3 is acceptable); SRMR=.0651 (<.8 is acceptable); GFI=.828 (>0.90 is acceptable); AGFI=.795 (>.8 is acceptable); NFI=.879 (>.9 is acceptable); CFI=.922 (>.9 is acceptable); PCFI=.827 (>.8 is acceptable); RMSEA=.067 (>.08 is acceptable); TLI=.913 (>.9 is acceptable); IFI=.922 (>.9 is acceptable).

To sum up, the results show that the data used in this study fit the model well. The output of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis and the overall fit indices are shown in Table 7 and Figure 16 below:

MODEL	CMIN/DF	SRMR	GFI	AGFI	NFI	CFI	PCFI	RMSEA	TLI	IFI
CFA Output	2.56/445	.0651	.828	.795	.879	.922	.827	.067	.913	.922
Cut-off Criteria	< 3	< .8	> .9	> .8	> .9	> .9	> .8	< .08	> .9	> .9

Table 7. Important statistical fit indices of CFA Analysis

Figure 16. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

5. Correlation Analysis

The correlation matrix (as presented in Table 9 below) reveals that there are strong and moderate significant positive correlations and associations between digital divide factors and public participation domains. First of all, ‘internet access’ has significant positive correlation with all other digital divide factors. There is a moderate Pearson’s correlation between internet access with internet use and digital literacy, ($r = .542^{**}$) and weak significant positive correlation with perceived benefit ($r = .446^{**}$). In addition, “internet access” has weak positive correlation ($r = .272^{**}$) with ‘social participation’ and moderate positive correlation ($r = .648^{**}$) with ‘political participation’. Furthermore, ‘internet use’ has moderate significant positive correlation with internet access ($r = .542^{**}$) and perceived benefit ($r = .626^{**}$) and strong positive correlation with digital literacy ($r = .736^{**}$). Nevertheless, “internet use” has weak positive correlation with ‘social participation’ ($r = .379^{**}$) and moderate positive association with ‘political participation’ ($r = .501^{**}$). Perceived benefit and digital literacy are also positively correlated with each other at $.508^{**}$ as well as with the domains of public participation. The dependent variables (social participation and political participation) are also significantly correlated to each other at $.490^{**}$.

Variables		1	2	3	4	5	6
Internet Access	Pearson Correlation	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed) = .000						
Internet Use	Pearson Correlation	.542**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed) = .000						
Digital Literacy	Pearson Correlation	.542**	.736**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed) = .000						
Perceived Benefit	Pearson Correlation	.446**	.626**	.508**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed) = .000						
Social Participation	Pearson Correlation	.272**	.379**	.424**	.429**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed) = .000						
Political Participation	Pearson Correlation	.648**	.501**	.577**	.398**	.490**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed) = .000						

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 8. Independent and Dependent Variables' Correlation Matrix

6. Hypothesis Testing and Analysis

To test the hypotheses in this study, I used a series of ordinary least-squares regressions (OLS) and Pearson's R correlations to define the strength and direction of the effect of digital divide on the various domains of mass participation. The concepts of digital divide and public participation are analyzed and measured by the various indicators illustrated in Appendix I.

In the first analysis, I utilized bivariate Pearson's R analyses to discover the strength of each of the four dimensions of digital divide on public participation. Using the Pearson's R coefficients, I was able to find out the strength of the correlation between digital access, internet use, digital literacy, perceived benefit, and domains of public participation. Each of the four domains of digital divide is positively correlated with each other. This method allowed me to demonstrate the strength of the digital divide domains while preventing mythological violations with Ordinary Least Square regression analysis.

For the second analysis, I tested the impacts of the digital divide on public participation using Ordinary least square regression model that includes demographic control variables. As the final analysis, I tested the influence of the digital divide on the individual participation domain through a series of OLS regressions, in which the β coefficients are for each variable are compared across domains. In each analysis, the omnibus Digital Divide serves as an independent variable to prognosticate levels of public participation alongside a number of control variables. These control variables include gender, age, education level and household income level.

There is a positive correlation between internet access and public participation

In this analysis, I examine the correlation between internet access, social participation, and political participation. The strength of correlation between internet access and each domain of public participation is determined employing bivariate Pearson’s R correlation coefficients. The following two hypothesis were analyzed in this section:

H₁: There is a positive correlation between internet access and social participation.

H₂: There is a positive correlation between internet access and political participation.

Correlations

	Internet Access	Social Participation	Political Participation
Pearson Correlation	1	.272**	.648**
Internet Access Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
N	354	354	354

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 9. Pearson’s R Coefficients: Internet Access on Social and Political Participation

Hypothesis Test

The correlation between internet access and social and political participation was statistically significant. To test hypothesis 1 and 2, I used the Pearson’s R coefficients to check the correlation between the two variables. I, therefore, hypothesize that people with higher level of access to internet will be more engaged in social and political activities focused on this study. Referring to the table 9, the correlation coefficient between internet access and political participation (.648**) is stronger than that of social participation (.272**), indicating that people with higher levels of internet access enjoy higher levels of political participation and are less engaged in social activities. Considering the results,

Hypotheses 1 and 2 are supported.

There is a positive correlation between internet use and public participation

For this analysis, I examine the correlation between internet use, social participation, and political participation. The strength of correlation between internet use and each domain of public participation is determined employing bivariate Pearson’s R correlation coefficients. The following two hypothesis were analyzed in this section:

H3: There is a positive correlation between internet use and social participation.

H4: There is a positive correlation between internet use and political participation.

		Internet Use	Social Participation	Political Participation
Internet Use	Pearson Correlation	1	.379**	.501**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	354	354	354

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 10.

Pearson’s R Coefficients: Internet Use on Social and Political Participation

Hypothesis Test

The correlations between internet use, social and political participation were statistically significant. To test hypothesis 3 and 4, I used the Pearson’s R coefficients to check the correlation between the two variables. Referring to above correlation statistics, I hypothesize that people with higher level of internet use will be more engaged in social and political activities focused on this study. The correlation coefficient between internet access and political participation (.501**) is stronger than that of social participation (.379**), indicating that people with higher levels of internet use enjoy higher levels of political participation and are less engaged in social activities. Considering the results,

Hypotheses 3 and 4 are also supported.

Higher level of digital literacy leads to higher level of public participation

In this section, I examine the correlation between digital literacy, social participation, and political participation as well as the influence of the digital divide on social participation in compared to socio-economic control variables. For the first analysis, I find the strength of correlation between internet access and each domain of public participation employing bivariate Pearson’s R correlation coefficients. For the second analysis, I run an OLS Regression to find out which dependent variables (social participation or SEM) are affected the most by the digital divide. The following two hypothesis were analyzed in this section:

H5: Digital literacy is correlated the most with a higher level of political participation as compared to social participation.

H6: Digital literacy has the strongest positive influence on social participation when compared to social-economic status (SES) variables.

Hypothesis Test: correlations analysis

Below table explains the correlations between digital literacy and public participation domains.

Correlations

	Digital Literacy	Social Participation	Political Participation
Pearson Correlation	1	.424**	.577**
Digital Literacy Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
N	354	354	354

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 11.

Pearson’s R Coefficients: Digital Literacy on Social and Political Participation

The correlations between internet access and public participation domains were statistically significant. To test hypothesis 5, I used the Pearson's R coefficients to check the correlation between the two variables. I, therefore, hypothesize that people with higher level of digital literacy will be more engaged in social and political activities which are focused on this study. Referring to the table 11, the correlation coefficient between digital literacy and political participation (.577**) is stronger than that of social participation (.424**), indicating that people with higher levels of digital literacy enjoy higher levels of political participation and are less engaged in social activities. Considering the results, Hypothesis 5 is supported as well.

Hypothesis Test: OLS Regression Model

In this analysis, I used an OLS Regression to test the 6th hypothesis on to what extent the independent variables of digital literacy and SES affect social participation and which one's affect is stronger? Table 12 demonstrates the results of the regression analysis:

Coefficients - Dependent Variable: Social Participation

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		
	β	Std. Error	Sig.
(Constant)	1.747	.205	.000
Digital Literacy	.346	.062	.000
Age	-.103	.049	.083
Gender	.161	.106	.002
Education	-.005	.069	.942
Income	.005	.054	.932
R ²	.206		.000
Adjusted R ²	.195		
Durbin-Watson	1.781		

Dependent Variable: Social-Participation

Regression Equation: Social-Participation = a + B(Age) + B(Gender) + B(Education) + B(Income) + e

Table 12.

Regression Results of Digital Literacy and SES on Social Participation

In this analysis, social participation is the dependent variable. To analyze the strength of the effects, I compared the beta coefficients (β) and their statistical significance.

A beta coefficient compares the strength of the effect of individual independent variable to the dependent variable. “The higher the value of the beta coefficient, the stronger the effect.” As shown in the table, the highest beta coefficient in table 12 belongs to Digital Literacy ($\beta = .818^{**}$), confirming as the strongest and significant predictor of social participation when compared to socio-economic variables. Considering the results, Hypothesis 6 is also supported.

Higher level of perceived benefit leads to higher level of public participation

In this section, I test the influence of perceived benefit on political participation while comparing it with other three dimensions of the digital divide, namely internet access, internet use and digital literacy. In addition, I examine the correlation of the perceived benefit with social and political participation, to check which one’s correlated is stronger. For the first analysis, I run an OLS Regression to find out which dependent variables (social participation or public participation) are affected the most by the perceived benefit. For the second analysis, I discover the strength of correlation between perceived benefit and each domain of public participation, utilizing bivariate Pearson’s R correlation coefficients. The following two hypothesis were analyzed in this section:

H₇: Perceived Benefit influences political participation the most when compared to other three dimensions of the digital divide, namely internet access, internet use, and digital literacy.

H₈: Perceived Benefit is correlated the most with a higher level of political participation

compared to social participation.

Hypothesis Test: OLS Regression Analysis Model

In this section, I conducted an OLS regression model to demonstrate how digital divide influences the public participation. I decided to combine the four domains of digital divide into a single, omnibus variable, considering the fact that all four domains are correlated and can work together as well. In this analysis, omnibus public participation is the dependent variable. To analyze the strength of the correlation, I compared the beta coefficients (β) and the statistical significance of the test.

Table 13 demonstrates the results of this regression analysis:

Independent Variables	Social Participation			Political Participation		
	β	Std. Error	Sig.	β	Std. Error	Sig.
(Constant)	.820	.205	.000	-.252	.213	.238
Internet Access	-.007	.052	.886	.529	.054	.000
Internet Use	-.012	.070	.861	.004	.073	.956
Digital Literacy	.239	.059	.000	.321	.061	.000
Perceived Benefit	.298	.061	.000	.042	.064	.508
R ²	.241		.000	.493		.000
Adjusted R ²	.233			.487		
R Square Change	.241			.493		
F Value	27.735			84.791		
Durbin-Watson	1.806			1.718		

Table 13.

Results of OLS Regression Analysis: Digital Divide on Public Participation

H7: Perceived Benefit influences political participation the most when compared to other three dimensions of the digital divide, namely internet access, internet use, and digital literacy.

As indicate in the table, the highest beta coefficient in the table 13 belongs to internet access as the strongest and significant predictor of political participation ($\beta = .529^{**}$)

while perceived benefit has one of the smallest coefficients ($\beta = .042^{**}$) which is not even statistically significant. Considering the results, Hypothesis 7 is not supported.

Additionally, perceived benefit has the strongest positive significant influence on social participation ($\beta = .298^{**}$), followed by digital literacy ($\beta = .239^{**}$). On the other hand, internet access and digital literacy have the strongest positive influence on political participation respectively at $\beta = .529^{**}$ and $\beta = .321^{**}$.

It is important to consider the effects of other variables as well. As indicated in the above table, internet access and internet use do not have statistically significant influence on social participation. Because, the variable “social participation” can also be considered as offline social participation, due to the fact that the items that are used to measure this variable are all related to offline participation. However, the case is not applicable to political participation, as the items used to measure political participation are a mixture of online and offline activities.

Hypothesis Test: correlations analysis

Below table explains the correlations between perceived benefit and two domains of public participation (social and political participation):

Correlations

	Perceived Benefit	Social Participation	Political Participation
Perceived Benefit	Pearson Correlation	1	.429**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	354	354

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 14.
Pearson’s R Coefficients: Digital Literacy on Social and Political Participation

As per the output of the analysis, the correlations between perceived benefit and public participation domains were statistically significant at $p < 0.005$. To test hypothesis 8, I used the Pearson's R coefficients to check the correlation between the two variables. I, therefore, hypothesize that people who show a higher level of perceived benefit will have more engagement in social and political activities which are focused on this study. Referring to the table 14, the correlation coefficient between perceived benefit and social participation (.429**) is stronger than that of political participation (.398**), indicating that people with higher levels of perceived benefit enjoy higher levels of social participation in compared to political participation. Considering the results, Hypothesis 8 is not supported.

Lower level of digital divide leads to higher level of political participation

In this section, I conducted an OLS regression model to demonstrate how digital divide influences the public participation. I decided to combine the four domains of digital divide into a single, omnibus variable, considering the fact that all four domains are correlated and can work together as well. In this analysis, omnibus public participation is the dependent variable. To analyze the strength of the correlation, I compared the beta coefficients (β) and the statistical significance of the test. Table 15 and 16 demonstrate the results of this regression analysis. I employed this regression to either confirm or reject the following hypothesis:

H₉: Digital divide has the strongest positive influence on public participation when compared to social-economic status (SES) as control variable.

H₁₀: Lower level of digital divide leads to higher level of political participation.

Coefficients: Public Participation

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		
	β	Std. Error	Sig.
(Constant)	-.403	.238	.090
Digital Divide	.818	.071	.000
Age	.122	.042	.004
Gender	.234	.087	.007
Education	-.023	.056	.681
Income	-.003	.045	.945
R ²	.457		.000
Adjusted R ²	.449		
Durbin-Watson	1.759		

Dependent Variable: Public Participation

Regression Equation: Public-Participation = a + B(Age) + B(Gender) + B(Education) + B(Income) + e

Table 15.

Regression Results of Digital Divide and SES on Public Participation

Coefficients: Political Participation

Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		
	β	Std. Error	Sig.
(Constant)	-.582	.207	.005
Digital Divide	.909	.056	.000
R ²	.424		.000
Adjusted R ²	.422		
Durbin-Watson	1.504		

Dependent Variable: Public Participation

Regression Equation: Public-Participation = a + B(Age) + B(Gender) + B(Education) + B(Income) + e

Table 16. Regression Results of Digital Divide on Political Participation

Hypothesis Test: OLS Regression Analysis and Correlation

As indicated in the table, the highest beta coefficient in table 15 is the digital divide ($\beta = .818^{**}$) which is considered as the strongest and significant predictor of public participation in compared to socio-economic control variables. Referring to Table 16, the digital divide is also a strong predictor of political participation as well. Considering the results, Hypotheses 8 and 9 are supported. This finding denotes that even in the existence

of other variables that could affect an individual's level of public participation, digital divide strongly predicts his/her participation. Thus, as a person's level of digital divide decreases, the level of their public participation increases. Moreover, the Age and Gender variables are also statistically significant, which indicate that those who are younger are more active in public participation than those who are older, and the level of participation among female are lower in compared to male. It is also important to consider the effects of other variables as well. As indicated in the above table, Education and Income are not statistically significant in the model of this study. Although education and money are two important resources that support public participation, it seems that those variables have no effect on one's public participation in this study. Thus, people of all income levels and education level might be participating equally, considering the fact that the variables are not significant.

Bias Testing Through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

The univariate Kurtoses and Skewness fall between +2 and -2. The researcher also checked the "biasedness" through performing a bootstrap using the default values set by AMOS (200 number of bootstrap samples and 90% Bias-correlated confidence level). Referring to the Bias column, the bias for all the items falls between -.005 and +.004, which is considerably minimum. Thus, we can be assured that there is very little bias in the model caused by factors such as non-normality.

Summary of the Hypothesis Testing

HYPOTHESIS	Coefficient	Sig. Value (2-tailed)	Interpretation	Result
H1: There is a positive correlation between internet access and social participation	.648**	.000	Significant correlation between internet access and social participation. Hypothesis is supported.	✓
H2: There is a positive correlation between internet access and political participation.	.272**	.000	Significant correlation between internet access and political participation. Hypothesis is supported.	✓
H3: There is a positive correlation between internet use and social participation.	.379**	.000	Significant correlation between internet use and social participation. Hypothesis is supported.	✓
H4: There is a positive correlation between internet use and political participation.	.501**	.000	Significant correlation between internet use and political participation. Hypothesis is supported.	✓
H5: Digital literacy is correlated the most with a higher level of political participation compared to social participation.	PP = .577** SP = .424**	.000	Digital literacy is correlated the most with higher levels of political participation. Hypothesis is supported.	✓
H6: Digital literacy has the strongest positive influence on social participation when compared to social-economic status (SES) variables.	SP = .346** SES = .161**	.000	Digital literacy has the strongest positive influence on social participation. Hypothesis is supported.	✓
H7: Perceived Benefit has the strongest positive influence on political participation when compared to other three dimensions of the digital divide, namely internet access, internet use, and digital literacy.	PP = .042** DD = .298**	.000	Perceived benefit does not influence political participation the most, compared to internet access, use and digital literacy. Hypothesis is not supported.	✗
H8: Perceived Benefit is correlated the most with a higher level of political participation compared to social participation.	PP = .398** SP = .429**	.000	Perceived Benefit is not correlated the most with a higher level of social participation. Hypothesis is not supported.	✗
H9: Digital divide has the strongest positive influence on public participation when compared to social-economic status (SES) as control variable.	DD = .818** SES < .234**	.000	Digital divide has the strongest positive influence on public participation. Hypothesis is supported.	✓
H10: Lower level of digital divide lead to higher level of public participation.	$\beta = .818^{**}$.000	A lower level of digital divide leads to higher level of public participation. Hypothesis is supported.	✓

Table 17. Results of Hypothesis Testing

VI. CONCLUSION

1. Findings and Conclusions

In this thesis, I examined the relationship and influence of digital divide dimensions on two types of public participation, namely social and political participation, by asking the following research question: To what degree the digital divide influences the public participation? As such, the main argument the author presents in this thesis is that digital divide is influencer of public participation. Those who possess low levels of digital divide are significantly empowered to participate socially and politically in the society, and as a result of this, they enjoy higher levels of access to information, opportunities, services, and influence on effect social outcomes.

Any research undertaking in the social sciences must confront and answer the following questions: what is the evidence on which the study bases its conclusions? And how reliable is that evidence? Using data from the surveys of 385 respondents in the Kabul Province, I presented evidence to test 10 hypotheses and support the arguments of this study. The analysis done in previous chapters elaborate the key findings of this thesis that is: the digital divide has significant impact on social and political participation. It is also tested that those groups with widened digital divide are less empowered to participate. In this section I focus on some of the key findings this thesis has proven.

First, I found that internet access and internet use are significantly correlated with social and political participation, with a difference that their correlation coefficients in political activities are higher than that of social. This is due to the fact that there are no online activities among items used to measure social participation; thus, in this study the

social participation can also be called as “offline social participation.” Second, I found that people with higher levels of digital literacy will be more engaged in social and political activities that are focused on this study. The findings of the statistical test also indicate that people with higher levels of digital literacy enjoy higher levels of political participation and are less engaged in social activities. In addition, digital literacy is considered the strongest predictor of social participation when compared to other socio-economic variables (age, gender, education, and income). Third, after testing the influence of perceived benefit on political participation while comparing it with other three dimensions of the digital divide, namely internet access, internet use and digital literacy, the results indicate that internet access has the highest influence on political participation followed by digital literacy, while perceived benefit has the highest influence on social participation followed by the digital literacy. Fourth, examining the effects of digital divide, as an omnibus variable, and socio-economic variable on public participation and comparing the strength of their influences; the findings denote that even in the existence of other socio-economic variables (age, gender, education, income) that could affect an individual’s level of public participation, digital divide is considered as the strongest predictor. As a result, as a person’s level of digital divide decreases, the level of their public participation increases.

Utilizing a comparative test of the physical and technical development and their effect on individual's social and political participation, this study confirms the Technological Determinism Theory (TDT). As elaborated earlier, Technology Determinism Theory is a technology-based theory of social change; in which, the technology – technical development – is perceived as the main driver and principal

determinant of human relations, culture, and social structure, whereas the social factors are considered secondary.

2. Implications: theoretical, managerial, and policy

The conceptual framework of this study has been tested and verified in Kabul Province context, which explores the relationship of the digital divide dimensions on public participation domains. Additionally, this study provides the researchers and interest individuals with an in-depth and updated synthesizes of the literature on digital divide and public participation, particularly on internet access, internet use, digital literacy, internet perceived benefit, social participation, and political participation. Moreover, it includes and suggest some best practices on how to bridge the digital divide and foster technology adoption through focusing on underserved groups of individuals, especially women, elderly, and people living in remote areas.

Due to the lack of such research in Afghanistan context, the policies and strategies that have been recently developed by leading agencies dealing with e-Government implementation are lacking the desired credibility and reliability; thus, those policies and strategies are perceived to be unrealistic. The findings of this research will constitute a significant step for supporting the stakeholders, especially the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology (MCIT) in terms of technology implementation and will provide enough data about the roots and types of the digital divide as well as its impacts on people's culture in the society as a whole. Second, the ICT activists and enthusiasts and e-Government authorities can benefit this research to take action and find out solutions to eliminate the phenomenon of the digital divide and rectify

a portion of problems in the Afghan community. Third, this study will respectively assist the Ministry of Communications & Information Technology, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Women Affairs in developing new ICT policies, minimizing the gender gap using ICT means, and including digital literacy in the education curriculum.

To sum up, this work offers insights into the relationship of digital divide with political and demographic factors, explores the factors hindering or facilitating the process of bridging the digital divide, proposes solutions to digital divide-related concerns, analyzes the consequences of the presence or absence of digital divide, and assesses the cultural changes driven by ICT adoption. This study highlights the importance of technology and e-Government implementation in Afghanistan and recognizes them as pivotal to ensuring gender equality, digital literacy, quality of public service delivery, and overall national connectivity. Lastly, this study explains how the subject matter is of importance and worthy of study, and how the approach employed in this study is likely to lead the stakeholders to desirable results.

3. Limitations and Future Research

There are many limitations in this study and potential further research items that are beyond the capacity of this research, yet very relevant and important towards bridging the digital divide and enhancing the public participation.

The existing studies, including this, have indebtedly considered factors causing a digital divide, such as local economy, infrastructure, and demography, but have paid less or no attention to the political context and security challenges in crisis-hit countries. In Afghanistan and other war-torn countries, where local people typically suffer from

insecurity, the issue of digitization does not seem to be considered as their key priority, even though the economy affords, and the infrastructure is available. The second reason is associated with rough nature. Some rural areas are located far enough away from the local government and separated by rugged mountains from technology centers that hinder successful ICT penetration. Future research can examine the effects of rough nature on digital divide and e-Government service delivery to citizens living in remote areas. A third criticism of the study could represent the lack of attention to a series of intergovernmental and out-of-state circles who consider the implementation of large-scale technological projects as a risk to their interests and strive to prevent the implementation of such projects, which consequences nothing but a heightened digital divide. Fourth, due to the numerous numbers of variables in this study, the researcher decided to remove government initiatives as moderators, especially governmental online platforms/portals that facilitate the participation of people in government policymaking. Fifth, the number of respondents who took part in this study are limited as compared to the whole population; thus, it may not be appropriate to extrapolate the findings of this study to the whole country. Lastly, the researchers can explore other dimensions of digital divide and public participation as well, especially civic engagement in their future research. The above limitations could equally fit into the questions that future researchers can respond to.

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Appendix 1: Operationalization of the independent and dependent variables

Variables / Codes	Indicators (Operationalization)	Survey Items / Questions	Measure / Scale	Literature Support
Internet Access (Int_Acc)	Q1) On a 5-point scale (where 1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree), how do you rate your access to the internet in the last 3 months?			
	Individual's access to the Internet, by location	Q1a. I have regular and easy access to the internet at home.	<i>5-Point Scale:</i> 1) Strongly disagree 2) Disagree 3) Neutral 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree	(OECD, 2015); (International Telecommunication Union, 2020b) <i>(With some modifications)</i>
		Q1b. I have regular and easy access to the internet outside the home.		
		Q1c. I have regular and easy access to the internet Using a data plan on my mobile device.		
	Household internet speed	Q1d. The internet speed is appropriate in the area where I live.		(Alam & Salahuddin, 2015)
Internet Affordability	Q1e. The cost of the internet connection is reasonable for me.	(International Telecommunication Union, 2020b) (OECD, 2015); (International Telecommunication Union, 2020b); (Alam & Salahuddin, 2015); (Eshetu & Kinuthia, 2010)		
Internet Use (Int_Use)	Q2) How often do you use the Internet at different locations? On a 5-point scale (where 1=never and 5=daily).			
	Individual Internet use by location	Q2a. At home:	<i>5-Point Scale:</i> 1) Never 2) Once or twice a month 3) Once a week 4) Several times a week 5) Daily	(Union international telecommunication, 2014); (Reddick et al., 2020); (Masoumeh et al., 2013)
		Q2b. Outside home and public places such as a library, university,:		
		Q2c. Using a data plan on your mobile device:		
	Q3) How often do you use the internet to look for each of the following online activities? On a 5-point scale (where 1=never and 5=daily).			
	Personal development	Q3a. Online education or learning Q3b. Find vacancies/applying for jobs	<i>5-Point Scale:</i> 1) Never 2) Rarely 3) Once a month 4) Several times a month 5) All the time	(A. J. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014); (Epstein et al., 2011); (OECD, 2015); (Reddick et al., 2020); (Ng et al., 2019)
	Leisure	Q3c. Download music, video or watch TikTok for leisure		
Social interaction	Q3d. Send or receive emails			
	Q3e. Online social media or networking sites (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, ...)			
Information	Q3f. Online access to information (such as health, government services...)			
News	Q3g. Newspapers and online magazines			

Digital Literacy (Digi_Lit)	Q4) How capable or skillful are you with the following items related to technology and the internet? On a 5-point scale (where 1= not skillful at all and 5=very skillful).			
	Computer Literacy	Q4a. Using a computer to do basic things such as to get on the internet, send emails, and make documents		<p>(International Telecommunication Union, 2020b); (Vuorikari et al., 2016); (Riel, 2012b)</p> <p>(International Telecommunication Union, 2020a); (Union international telecommunication, (A. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2011); (UNESCO, 2018); (Al Khateeb et al., 2017); (Masoumeh et al., 2013); (Vuorikari et al.2016)</p> <p>(A. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2011); (UNESCO, 2018); (Al Khateeb et al., 2017); (Masoumeh et al., 2013)</p> <p>(UNESCO, 2018); (Vuorikari et al., 2016); (Al Khateeb et al., 2017); (International Telecommunication Union, 2020b); (Masoumeh et al., 2013)</p>
		Q4b. Installing drivers or software on a new computer or device		
	Mobile Literacy	Q4c. Using a mobile phone to connect to the Internet to access websites or social networks.		
	Information processing skills	Q4d. Using search engines (e.g., Google) to find websites/documents		
		Q4e. Saving information found on the internet in different formats.		
	Communication	Q4f. Sharing information, photos, and videos on using email or social network websites (such as Facebook or Twitter)		
	Content Creation	Q4g. Creating and editing text documents with a Microsoft Word		
Q4h. Creating and editing videos				
Safety	Q4i. Online privacy and keeping your personal information secure			
	Q4j. Identifying fake and misleading information, websites, or emails on the Internet			
Perceived Benefit	Q5) Please indicate how each of the following statements describes your feelings or your life experience with the Internet.			
	Attitudes towards internet	Q5a. I feel positive about the use of the Internet.		<p>(Reddick et al., 2020); (Riel, 2012a); (Alam & Salahuddin, 2015)</p> <p>(A. J. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014);</p> <p>(A. J. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014); (UNESCO, 2018)</p> <p>(A. J. van Deursen & van Dijk, 2014); (Reddick et al., 2020); (Alam & Salahuddin, 2015); (Kim & Lee, 2012)</p> <p>(Riel, 2012a)</p>
	Relationship maintenance	Q5b. Internet and mobile phone maintain my relationship with my family, friends, and acquaintances in society.		
	Entertainment	Q5c. Digital means (internet, mobile phone, and PC) help me have fun and entertain myself.		
	Career	Q5d. The internet has a positive impact on my career performance.		
	Personal development	Q5e. I believe I make effective use of the internet.		
Relative advantage (DOI)	Q5f. Technology skills give regular people a greater opportunity to make a difference in their communities and the country compared to traditional approaches.			

Public Participation

Q6. On a scale of 1 to 5, please choose the level of your agreement to the following statements about your social engagement in the last three months.				
Offline Social Participation (Off_Soc)	Attend religious activities	Q6a. I have been involved in Masjid or religious activities.	<i>5-Point Scale:</i> 1) Strongly disagree 2) Disagree 3) Neutral 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree	(Zukin et al., 2006); (Riel, 2012b); (Barnidge et al., 2014); (Man, 2010)
	Attend community events	Q6b. I have been involved in community events or campaigns (festivals)		
	Attend sports activities	Q6c. I have been involved in sports or outdoors club activities		
	Attend public presentations	Q6d. I have attended several public presentations, speeches, or lectures.		(Barnidge et al., 2014); (Alam & Salahuddin, 2015); (Man, 2010)
	Join social groups	Q6e. I have Participated in groups that take local action for social reform.		(Man, 2010)
Online Social Participation (Onl_Civ)	Meet online friends	Q6f. I have had real-life meetings/events with people I met online.	<i>5-Point Scale:</i> 1) Strongly disagree 2) Disagree 3) Neutral 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree	(Riel, 2012a); (Alam & Salahuddin, 2015)
	Plan social activities using the internet	Q6g. I have used the Internet to plan activities with family and friends.		
	Online discussions	Q6h. I have had online discussions with people in my society who share my interests.		(Alam & Salahuddin, 2015); (Kim & Lee, 2012)
	Perceptions on the use of internet in the civic activities	Q6i. The Internet has helped me become socially more active compared to when I did not have the Internet. Q6j. I believe that the public needs technology and Internet skills to work and live in a society today.		
Q7. In the last three months, at what level did you participate in the following political activities?				
Offline Political Participation (Off_Pol)	Watch or listen to political debates on TV/radio	Q7a. I have watched or listened to political debates on TV or radio.	<i>5-Point Scale:</i> 1) Strongly disagree 2) Disagree 3) Neutral 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree	(Man, 2010); (Riel, 2012a)
	Read newspapers	Q7b. I have read newspapers and magazines on political issues.		(Vesnic-Alujevic, 2012); (Valenzuela et al., 2012) (Mortimer, 2015); (Man, 2010)
	Contact a government official in person	Q7c. I have met/contacted a government official in person/by phone.		
	Discuss political issues in person	Q7d. I have discussed political issues with people in person.		(Man, 2010); (Vesnic-Alujevic, 2012); (Riel, 2012a)
	Participate in a group	Q7e. I have participated in groups that take local action for		

	in person	political reform		
	Participate in a demonstration	Q7f. I have participated in demonstrations or boycotts.		
	Call or write to a newly elected public official	Q7g. I have called or written to a newly elected public official.		(Valenzuela et al., 2012); (Bulkova, 2010); (Man, 2010);

Online Political Participation (Onl_Pol)	Q8. On a 5-point scale (where 1=never and 5=All the time) how often you used the Internet for the following activities?			
	Look for information about politics	Q8a. I have looked online for news or information about politics.	<i>5-Point Scale:</i> 1) Strongly disagree 2) Disagree 3) Neutral 4) Agree 5) Strongly Agree	(Gil De Zúñiga et al., 2009); (Man, 2010);
	Look for information about government	Q8b. I have looked for information from government websites.		(Valenzuela et al., 2012); (Riel, 2012a); (Alam & Salahuddin, 2015)
	Send e-mails or messages with a political content	Q8c. I have sent e-mails/messages with political content to another person.		(Santana, 2017); (Cohen & Kahne, 2018); (Towner, 2013)
	Follow/like a fan page of a politician	Q8d. I have followed or become a fan of political figures on social media platforms.		(Man, 2010); (Riel, 2012a)
	Post political comments	Q8e. I have posted comments/web links on social media or websites to express political opinions.		
	Participate in online chats on politics	Q8f. I have taken part in discussions online or participated in chat groups on politics.		
	Support on social media	Q8g. I have displayed images on social media or websites to support a candidate or a political issue (such as a Facebook profile picture).		
Perception of the use of the internet in politics	Q8h. I believe I and regular people can make government officials listen to us in politics today by using technology and the Internet.			

APPENDIX II: Survey Questionnaire

Dear Participant:

You are invited to participate in a research study titled “From the Digital Divide to Mass Participation: An Exploration of the Citizens’ Perceptions in Afghanistan.” This study is being conducted by Rashid ZARA, a graduate student at SungKyunKwan University, South Korea to examine the relationships between technology and citizen engagement.

In this survey, you will be requested to answer some questions about your use of technology and the level of participation in your society. The survey is comprised of 67 questions that should take approximately 13-15 minutes of your time to complete.

For your information, studies have proven that public participation is a key catalyst for national development, knowledge creation, and circulation of information which also encourages a sense of responsibility amongst the community. Since modern communities are not homogeneous but indeed heterogeneous, for a society it is essential to benefit from the opinions of all its members through their “participation” in civic and political activities. In this case, the results of this research, with your contribution, fills the gap in the literature, supports the government in policymaking through the incorporation of your opinions, and assists concerning stakeholders, including the private sector and international community, in their attempts to narrowing the digital divide and empowering the public participation in Afghanistan.

All of your answers to this survey remain anonymous and will be kept confidential. No information about you will be collected during the study and all your responses will be used for academic purposes only. If you have any questions regarding the survey or research project in general, please do not hesitate to email me.

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Section A. Internet Access

1. On a 5-point scale (where 1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree), how do you rate your access to the internet ?		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
		①	②	③	④	⑤
1.1	I have regular and easy access to the internet at home.	<input type="radio"/>				
1.2	I have regular and easy access to the internet outside the home.	<input type="radio"/>				
1.3	I have regular and easy access to the internet using a data plan on my mobile device.	<input type="radio"/>				
1.4	The internet speed is appropriate in the area where I live.	<input type="radio"/>				
1.5	The price for internet connectivity is reasonable for me.	<input type="radio"/>				

Section B. Internet Use

How often do you use the Internet at the following different locations? <i>On a 5-point scale (where 1=never and 5=daily).</i>		Never	Rarely	Once in a month	Several times a month	All the time
		①	②	③	④	⑤
	At home.	<input type="radio"/>				
	Outside home and public places such as a library or university.	<input type="radio"/>				
	Using a data plan on your mobile device.	<input type="radio"/>				

2. How often do you use the internet to look for each of the following online activities ? <i>On a 5-point scale (where 1=never and 5=daily).</i>		Never	Rarely	Once in a month	Several times a month	All the time
		①	②	③	④	⑤
2.1	Online education or learning	<input type="radio"/>				
2.2	Find vacancies/applying for jobs	<input type="radio"/>				
2.3	Download music, video or using internet for pleasure	<input type="radio"/>				
2.4	Send or receive emails	<input type="radio"/>				
2.5	Online social media or networking sites (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, ...)	<input type="radio"/>				
2.6	Online access to information (such as health, government info...)	<input type="radio"/>				
2.7	Newspapers and online magazines	<input type="radio"/>				

Section C. Digital Literacy

3. How capable or skillful are you with the following items related to technology and the internet? <i>On a 5-point scale (where 1= not skillful at all and 5=very skillful).</i>		Not skillful at all	Not very skillful	Somewhat skillful	Skillful	Very skillful
		①	②	③	④	⑤
3.1	Using a computer to do basic things such as to get on the internet, send emails, and make documents.	<input type="radio"/>				
3.2	Installing drivers or software on a new computer or device.	<input type="radio"/>				
3.3	Using a mobile phone to connect to the Internet to access websites or social networks.	<input type="radio"/>				
3.4	Using search engines (e.g., Google) to find websites/documents	<input type="radio"/>				
3.5	Saving information found on the internet in different formats.	<input type="radio"/>				
3.6	Sharing information, photos, and videos on using email or social network websites (such as Facebook or Twitter).	<input type="radio"/>				
3.7	Creating and editing text documents with a Microsoft Word.	<input type="radio"/>				
3.8	Creating and editing videos.	<input type="radio"/>				
3.9	Online privacy and keeping your personal information secure.	<input type="radio"/>				
3.10	Identifying fake and misleading information, websites, or emails on the Internet.	<input type="radio"/>				

Section D. Perceived Benefit

4. Please indicate how each of the following statements describes your feelings or your life experience with the Internet? <i>On a 5-point scale (where 1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree).</i>		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
		①	②	③	④	⑤
4.1	I feel positive about the use of the Internet.	<input type="radio"/>				
4.2	Internet and mobile phone maintain my relationship with my family, friends, and acquaintances in society.	<input type="radio"/>				
4.3	Digital means (internet, mobile phone, and PC) help me have fun and entertain myself.	<input type="radio"/>				
4.4	The internet has a positive impact on my career performance.	<input type="radio"/>				
4.5	I believe I make effective use of the internet.	<input type="radio"/>				
4.6	I believe technology skills give me and the public a greater opportunity to make a difference in the community and the country.	<input type="radio"/>				

Section E. Social Participation

5. Please choose the level of your agreement to the following statements about your social activities? <i>On a 5-point scale (where 1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree).</i>		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
		①	②	③	④	⑤
5.1	I have been involved in Masjid or religious activities.	<input type="radio"/>				
5.2	I have been involved in community events or campaigns or festivals.	<input type="radio"/>				
5.3	I have been involved in sports or outdoors club activities.	<input type="radio"/>				
5.4	I have attended several public presentations, speeches, or lectures.	<input type="radio"/>				
5.5	I have participated in groups that take local action for social reform.	<input type="radio"/>				
5.6	I have had real-life meetings or events with people I met online.	<input type="radio"/>				
5.7	I have used the Internet to plan activities with family and friends.	<input type="radio"/>				
5.8	I have had online discussions with people in my society who share my interests.	<input type="radio"/>				
5.9	The Internet has helped me become socially more active compared to when I did not have the Internet.	<input type="radio"/>				
5.10	The public needs stronger technology and Internet skills to work and live in a society today.	<input type="radio"/>				

Section F. Political Participation

6. At what level have you participated in the following political activities?		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
		①	②	③	④	⑤
6.1	I have watched or listened to political debates on TV or radio.	<input type="radio"/>				
6.2	I have read newspapers and magazines on political issues.	<input type="radio"/>				
6.3	I have contacted a government official in person or by phone.	<input type="radio"/>				
6.4	I have discussed political issues with people in person.	<input type="radio"/>				
6.5	I have participated in groups that take local actions for political reform	<input type="radio"/>				
6.6	I have participated in demonstrations or boycotts.	<input type="radio"/>				
6.7	I have called or written to a newly elected public official.	<input type="radio"/>				

7. How often do you use the Internet for the following activities? <i>On a 5-point scale (where 1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree).</i>		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
		①	②	③	④	⑤
7.1	I have looked online for news or information about politics.	<input type="radio"/>				
7.2	I have looked for information from government websites.	<input type="radio"/>				
7.3	I have sent e-mails/messages with political content to another person.	<input type="radio"/>				
7.4	I have followed political figures on social media platforms.	<input type="radio"/>				
7.5	I have posted comments/web links on social media or websites to express	<input type="radio"/>				

	political opinions.					
7.6.	I have taken part in discussions online or participated in chat groups on politics.	<input type="radio"/>				
7.7	I have displayed images on social media or websites to support a candidate or a political issue (such as a Facebook profile picture).	<input type="radio"/>				
7.8	I believe I and regular people can make government officials listen to us in politics today by using technology and the Internet.	<input type="radio"/>				

Section G. Social Demographic Information

For each question below, please mark your response with a tick , unless otherwise indicated. As for ‘Other’ responses, please provide a brief response.

57. In which district do you live? (District number)

58. How old are you?

59. What is your gender? Male Female

60. What is your marital status? Single Married

61. What is your highest level of education?

None Primary Secondary Undergraduate Postgraduate Ph.D.

62. How is your employment status?

Looking for Job Civil Service/Public Service Education/Teaching
Trading/Business Medical/Health Computer/ICT Banking/Insurance Other

63. What is your monthly household income level?

Below 20,000 AFS 20,000 - 50,000 AFS 50,000 - 100,000 AFS
 \$100,000 - 150,000 AFS 150,000 - 200,000 AFS Over 200,000 AFS

64. Including yourself, how many people live in your household? (please specify)

65. How many children (under the age of 18) live in your household?

1 2 3 4 5 more than 5

66. How do you rate your English language skills for the needs of everyday life (e.g., work, reading newspapers, understanding, and filling in forms)?

Very Bad Bad Fair Good Excellent

67. Which of the following devices do you own? (Check the ones that you own)

Cell phone without internet Smartphone that has the capability of 3G/4G
 PC (Laptop or Desktop) Tablet

68. How many computers (desktop and laptop) are there in your household?

0 1 2 3 4 more than 4

“Set your life on fire. Seek those who fan your flames” — Rumi

ضمیمه ۲: پرسشنامه برای نظرسنجی

شرکت‌کننده گرامی!

از شما دعوت می‌شود در تحقیق علمی تحت عنوان "از شکاف دیجیتال تا مشارکت عمومی: بررسی دیدگاه شهروندان در افغانستان" شرکت کنید. این مطالعه توسط رشید ذره، دانشجوی ماستری (کارشناسی‌ارشد) در دانشگاه Sungkyunkwan کوریای جنوبی، انجام می‌شود تا رابطه میان تکنولوژی و مشارکت مردمی را در افغانستان مورد بررسی قرار دهد.

در این پرسشنامه از شما درخواست می‌شود تا به برخی سوالات در مورد نحوه استفاده شما از تکنولوژی و سطح مشارکت‌تان در جامعه پاسخ دهید. این نظرسنجی از ۶۸ سوال تشکیل شده است که حدود ۱۳ تا ۱۵ دقیقه وقت‌تان را در بر می‌گیرد.

محض اطلاع شما، تحقیقات ثابت ساخته است، مشارکت عمومی عامل اصلی توسعه ملی، ایجاد دانش و انتشار اطلاعات است که همزمان احساس مسئولیت در میان اعضای جامعه را نیز به وجود می‌آورد. از آنجا که جوامع مدرن متشکل از افراد با دیدگاه‌های متفاوت است، بنابراین برای یک جامعه مهم است که از نظرات تمام اعضا از طریق "مشارکت" آن‌ها در فعالیت‌های مدنی و سیاسی بهره‌مند شود. با اشتراک‌تان در این نظرسنجی، کمک می‌کنید تا خلاء موجود در ادبیات پر گردد. همچنین دولت و سایر نهادها ذیربط می‌توانند با استفاده از نتایج این تحقیق و از طریق ادغام نظریات شما در روند سیاستگذاری و پالیسی‌سازی، شکاف دیجیتال موجود را محدود ساخته و در راستای تقویت مشارکت عمومی در افغانستان گام‌های مؤثر بردارند.

هیچ نوع اطلاعاتی خصوصی در مورد شما در طول این مطالعه جمع‌آوری نخواهد شد و تمام پاسخ‌های شما صرفاً برای اهداف علمی و تحصیلی مورد استفاده قرار خواهد گرفت. اگر شما سوالی در مورد پرسشنامه یا تحقیق به طور کلی دارید، لطفاً به آدرس الکترونیک ذیل ایمیل بفرستید.

رشید ذره

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ممنون از اشتراک‌تان!

بخش اول: سطح دسترسی به اینترنت

کاملاً مخالف	مخالف	بدون نظر	موافق	کاملاً موافق	
①	②	③	④	⑤	
○	○	○	○	○	1. در یک مقیاس 1 الی 5 نمره‌ی (که در آن 1=کمترین و 5=بیشترین دسترسی را نشان می‌دهد)، سطح دسترسی‌تان را به اینترنت چگونه ارزیابی می‌کنید؟
○	○	○	○	○	1.1 در خانه، به اینترنت دسترسی آسان و منظم دارم.
○	○	○	○	○	1.2 در خارج از خانه، به اینترنت دسترسی آسان و منظم دارم.
○	○	○	○	○	1.3 با استفاده از بسته اینترنتی، به اینترنت دسترسی منظم و آسان دارم.
○	○	○	○	○	1.4 سرعت اینترنت در منطقه‌ای که من در آن زندگی می‌کنم، مناسب است.
○	○	○	○	○	1.5 هزینه اتصال به اینترنت برای من معقول و قابل پرداخت است.

بخش دوم: استفاده از اینترنت

هرگز	ماهی یک یا دو مرتبه	یک مرتبه در هفته	چندین مرتبه در هفته	همه‌روزه	
①	②	③	④	⑤	
○	○	○	○	○	2. در مکان‌های متفاوت ذیل، چقدر از اینترنت استفاده می‌کنید؟
○	○	○	○	○	2.1 استفاده از اینترنت در خانه:
○	○	○	○	○	2.2 استفاده از اینترنت در خارج از خانه (مکان‌های عمومی، کتابخانه، دانشگاه...):
○	○	○	○	○	2.3 با استفاده از بسته اینترنتی:

هرگز	ماهی یک یا دو مرتبه	یک مرتبه در هفته	چندین مرتبه در هفته	همه‌روزه	
①	②	③	④	⑤	
○	○	○	○	○	3. به چه اندازه از اینترنت برای انجام فعالیت‌های ذیل استفاده می‌کنید؟
○	○	○	○	○	3.1 آموزش یا تحصیل آنلاین
○	○	○	○	○	3.2 جستجوی کاریابی در وبسایت‌ها
○	○	○	○	○	3.3 دانلود موسیقی، ویدیو و یا جهت سرگرمی
○	○	○	○	○	3.4 ارسال و دریافت ایمیل
○	○	○	○	○	3.5 استفاده از شبکه‌های ارتباط جمعی، مثل: فیسبوک، توئیتر و ...
○	○	○	○	○	3.6 جستجو و دسترسی به اطلاعات عمومی
○	○	○	○	○	3.7 اخبار و مجلات آنلاین

بخش سوم: سواد دیجیتالی

اصلاً مهارت ندارم	بسیار کم مهارت دارم	کم مهارت دارم	مهارت دارم	بسیار مهارت دارم	
①	②	③	④	⑤	
○	○	○	○	○	4. در فعالیت‌های ذیل، مرتبط به اینترنت و استفاده از تکنولوژی، چقدر مهارت و توانایی دارید؟
○	○	○	○	○	4.1 استفاده از کامپیوتر برای انجام کارهای ابتدایی مانند ورود به اینترنت، ارسال ایمیل و تهیه اسناد.
○	○	○	○	○	4.2 نصب درایورها یا برنامه‌ها در کامپیوتر جدید.
○	○	○	○	○	4.3 استفاده از موبایل جهت دسترسی به وبسایت‌ها یا شبکه‌های اجتماعی.
○	○	○	○	○	4.4 استفاده از گوگل برای جستجو و دسترسی به وبسایت‌ها و مطالب.
○	○	○	○	○	4.5 ذخیره فایل‌های مختلف (مثل PDF، ویدیو و ...) در کامپیوتر با استفاده از اینترنت.
○	○	○	○	○	4.6 اشتراک اطلاعات، متن، عکس، یا ویدیو با استفاده از فیسبوک یا ایمیل.
○	○	○	○	○	4.7 ایجاد و ویرایش اسناد متنی با استفاده از Microsoft Word.
○	○	○	○	○	4.8 ایجاد و ویرایش ویدیو.
○	○	○	○	○	4.9 حریم خصوصی آنلاین و ایمن نگه داشتن اطلاعات شخصی.
○	○	○	○	○	4.10 شناسایی معلومات جعلی و گمراه کننده در اینترنت، وبسایت‌ها و ایمیل‌های جعلی.

بخش چهارم: سودمندی تکنولوژی

کاملاً موافق	موافق	بدون نظر	مخالف	کاملاً مخالف	5. چگونه هر یک از جملات ذیل احساس، دیدگاه و یا تجربه زندگی‌تان را با اینترنت توصیف می‌کنند؟
⑤	④	③	②	①	
<input type="radio"/>	5.1 در مورد استفاده از اینترنت احساس مثبت دارم.				
<input type="radio"/>	5.2 اینترنت و موبایل به من کمک می‌کند ارتباطم را با خانواده، دوستان و آشنایانم در جامعه حفظ کنم.				
<input type="radio"/>	5.3 ابزار دیجیتالی (اینترنت، موبایل، و کامپیوتر) برایم سرگرمی ایجاد می‌کند.				
<input type="radio"/>	5.4 اینترنت تأثیر مثبتی بر عملکرد شغلی من دارد.				
<input type="radio"/>	5.5 من معتقدم از اینترنت استفاده موثر می‌کنم.				
<input type="radio"/>	5.6 به این باور استم که تکنولوژی و مهارت‌های مرتبط به آن به من و به مردم فرصت بیشتری می‌دهد تا در جامعه و کشور تغییر ایجاد کنیم.				

بخش پنجم: مشارکت مدنی و فعالیت‌های اجتماعی

کاملاً موافق	موافق	بدون نظر	مخالف	کاملاً مخالف	6. لطفاً سطح مشارکت خود را در جامعه با استفاده از مقیاس 1 الی 5 بیان نمایید.
⑤	④	③	②	①	
<input type="radio"/>	6.1 در مسجد یا فعالیت‌های مذهبی فعال بوده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	6.2 در برنامه‌های اجتماعی و جشن‌های محلی دخیل بوده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	6.3 در فعالیت‌های ورزشی اشتراک داشته‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	6.4 در سخنرانی‌ها اشتراک کرده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	6.5 در برنامه‌های گروه‌ها و انجمن‌های که برای اصلاح اجتماعی فعالیت می‌کنند، اشتراک کرده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	6.6 با افرادی که به صورت آنلاین آشنا شده‌ام، دیدارهای حضوری نیز داشته‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	6.7 از اینترنت برای برنامه‌ریزی فعالیت‌های دوستانه، دیدارها و یا مسایل خانوادگی استفاده کرده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	6.8 با افراد جامعه خود که علایق مشترک داریم، بحث‌های آنلاین داشته‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	6.9 زمانی که اینترنت دارم در مقایسه با زمانی که اینترنت ندارم، از لحاظ اجتماعی فعال‌تر استم.				
<input type="radio"/>	6.10 عموم مردم به‌منظور کار و زندگی در جامعه امروزی به تکنولوژی و مهارت‌های اینترنتی نیاز دارند.				

بخش ششم: مشارکت سیاسی

کاملاً موافق	موافق	بدون نظر	مخالف	کاملاً مخالف	7. در چه سطحی در فعالیت‌های غیرانتزنی ذیل شرکت کرده‌اید؟
⑤	④	③	②	①	
<input type="radio"/>	7.1 مباحثات سیاسی را در تلویزیون یا رادیو تعقیب کرده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	7.2 روزنامه‌ها و مجلات کاغذی را در مورد مسائل سیاسی خوانده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	7.3 با یک مقام دولتی به صورت حضوری یا تلفنی تماس گرفته‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	7.4 به صورت حضوری در مورد مسائل سیاسی با مردم صحبت کرده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	7.5 در برنامه‌های گروه‌ها/انجمن‌های که برای اصلاح سیاسی فعالیت می‌کنند، اشتراک کرده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	7.6 در تظاهرات شرکت کرده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	7.7 به یک مقام دولتی که به تازگی استخدام شده‌است، جهت تبریگی تماس گرفته‌ام.				

کاملاً موافق	موافق	بدون نظر	مخالف	کاملاً مخالف	8. طی سه ماه گذشته، چقدر از اینترنت برای انجام فعالیت‌های انترنتی زیر استفاده کرده‌اید؟
⑤	④	③	②	①	
<input type="radio"/>	8.1 از اینترنت برای دسترسی به اخبار و اطلاعات در باره سیاست استفاده کرده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	8.2 جهت دریافت اطلاعات، به وبسایت‌های دولتی سر زده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	8.3 ایمیل یا پیام با محتوای سیاسی (یا دولتی) به شخص دیگری فرستاده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	8.4 چهره‌های مطرح سیاسی را در رسانه‌های اجتماعی (فیسبوک، تویت...) دنبال کرده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	8.5 در شبکه‌های اجتماعی در مورد موضوعات سیاسی (و دولتی) ابراز نظر کرده‌ام.				
<input type="radio"/>	8.6 در گروه‌های چت در رسانه‌های اجتماعی در مباحثات آنلاین درباره سیاست شرکت کرده‌ام.				

<input type="radio"/>	8.7	برای حمایت از یک کاندید انتخابات یا پست دولتی یا یک مساله سیاسی تصاویر را در رسانه‌های اجتماعی شریک ساخته ام (مثلاً تغییر تصویر پروفایل فیس بوک).				
<input type="radio"/>	8.8	به این باورم که من و مردم عادی می‌توانیم با استفاده از تکنولوژی و اینترنت مقامات دولتی و سیاستون را وادار کنیم تا به خواسته‌های ما گوش دهند.				

بخش هفتم: جمعیت‌شناسی

لطفاً جوابات درست را با نشانی کنید و در صورت درخواست معلومات به آن کوتاه پاسخ بدهید.

57. در کدام ناحیه شهر کابل زندگی می‌کنید؟

58. چند سال دارید؟

59. جنسیت: اناث ذکور

60. حالت تأهل: مجرد متأهل

61. سطح تحصیل: سند تحصیلی ندارم ابتدایه لیسه

لیسانس ماستری دکترا

62. در کدام عرصه وظیفه اجراء می‌کنید؟

ندارم (در جستجوی کار) کارمند دولت تدریس (استاد) شغل آزاد (تجارت)

صحت کامپیوتر و ICT مالی و بانکی سایر

63. به صورت تقریبی، درآمد ماهیانه خانواده شما چقدر است؟

کمتر از 20,000 افغانی 20,000 - 50,000 افغانی 50,000 - 100,000 افغانی

100,000 - 150,000 افغانی 150,000 - 200,000 افغانی بیشتر از 200,000 افغانی

64. به شمول شما، چند نفر دیگر در خانواده‌تان زندگی می‌کنند؟

65. چند کودک (پایین تر از سن ۱۸) در خانواده شما زندگی می‌کنند؟

0 1 2 3 4 5 یا بیشتر

66. از 1 الی 5، سطح مهارت زبان انگلیسی تان را در زندگی روزمره، کار، خواندن روزنامه و یا هنگام خانه‌پوری فورم چگونه ارزیابی می‌کنید؟

اصلاً انگلیسی بلد نیستم ابتدایی متوسط بسیار خوب عالی

67. از وسایل الکترونیک ذیل، کدام‌ها را دارید؟

موبایل بدون قابلیت اتصال به انترنت موبایل با قابلیت اتصال به انترنت

کامپیوتر (لپ‌تاپ یا دسک‌تاپ) تبلت

68. چند کامپیوتر (اعم از لپ‌تاپ و دسک‌تاپ) در خانه شما وجود دارد؟

0 1 2 3 بیشتر از 3

“Set your life on fire. Seek those who fan your flames” — Rumi

논문요약

논문제목을 작성하시오

제출자 성함(11p)

OO학과(11p)

성균관대학교(11p)

여기부터 논문요약을 한국어로 2page 이내(주제어 기재란 포함)로 작성하시기 바랍니다.